

Open letter by Scientists: **Climate Neutrality is Europe's Greatest Economic Opportunity**

Contact Persons:

*Prof. Dr. Dr. h.c. Hans-Otto Pörtner, Alfred Wegener Institut, Bremerhaven, Germany
<hans.poertner@awi.de>*

Prof. Dr. Charlotte Streck, University of Potsdam <streck1@uni-potsdam.de>

*Prof. Dr. Gottfried Kirchengast, Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change & Institute of
Physics, University of Graz, Graz, Austria <gottfried.kirchengast@uni-graz.at>*

*Dr. Guy Pe'er, UFZ – Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research and German Centre for
"Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig, Germany <guy.peer@idiv.de>*

*Dr. Gregor Hagedorn, Museum für Naturkunde – Leibniz Institute for Evolution and
Biodiversity Science, Berlin, Germany <gregor.hagedorn@mfn.berlin>*

*Prof. Dr.-Ing. Wulf-Peter Schmidt, CBS University of Applied Sciences, Cologne, Germany
<w.schmidt@cbs.de>*

Short Briefing

The European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change advised that a 90%–95% net domestic reduction of greenhouse gases (GHG) until 2040 (compared to the 1990 baseline) is necessary in order to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. The political discussion is moving further away from the scientific evidence, especially in the revision of the EU climate law (2040 climate target). Ahead of the summit of Heads of state and Heads of government on 23/10/2025, we urge policymakers to stick to science and stick to Paris. The EU should have submitted its target to the United Nations already in September – in time for the 2025 UN Climate Change Conference in November. A further delay or softening should not happen.

The European Commission has proposed a new EU climate target of at least 90% greenhouse gas reductions by 2040 compared to 1990 levels. This target is not arbitrary: it is based on scientific consensus pointing at an essential drastic reduction of GHG emissions and defining the minimum reduction which is needed to keep the EU on track for climate neutrality by 2050, as required under the EU Climate Law. The proposal builds directly on the findings of the European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change, which recommended a **domestic reduction of 90–95% by 2040** to remain consistent with the Paris Agreement.

The timing of the target is closely linked to international negotiations. The EU aims to **finalise the 2040 goal before COP30 in Belém in November 2025**. Entering those talks with a clear, science-based and credible 2040 target will strengthen Europe's negotiating power as a reliable and constructive global leader, on climate action in particular and international treaties in general. European leadership can encourage other countries and

regions to follow and create the necessary momentum towards decisive international actions.

A 2040 EU target of 90–95% reduction will also set a clear positive signal for science and humanity against recent misleading claims, like those of the Patriots for Europe group arguing that **climate change is not human made**¹. A further point of contention is the role of so-called “flexibilities.” Several governments are advocating the use of international offsets or external removals to count towards the target. The European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change, however, explicitly advises against such approaches. In its latest report, the Board calls on the EU to keep a high level of climate ambition when revising the Climate Law and recommends a domestic emissions reduction of 90–95% by 2040 as the pathway that best secures Europe’s long-term interests and ensures climate neutrality by 2050.² This is supported by a recent meta-study concluding that international carbon offsets are systematically inflated by a factor of 5-10 and are therefore not credible³.

The political discussion is moving further away from the scientific evidence provided by the European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change. Instead of focusing on a science-based pathway, negotiations are dominated by short-term politics, denialist motions that are based on misinformation, and bargaining over loopholes.

In this context, it is essential that the voices of the scientific community return to the centre of the debate, to remind heads of state and government ahead of EUCO on 23/10 that a 90%–95% net domestic reduction of greenhouse gases (GHG), compared to the 1990 level, is not just a political choice but an existential necessity for safeguarding Europe’s future, and securing people’s lives in face of increasingly high risks of surpassing critical tipping points⁴.

¹ “A word on science: Science is not unanimous – and climate models are uncertain. The recommendations of scientific bodies are neither infallible nor unanimous.”

https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/ENVI-PR-775698_EN.pdf

² <https://climate-advisory-board.europa.eu/news/staying-the-course-on-climate-action-essential-to-eu-security-and-competitiveness>

³ Romm, J., Lezak, S. & Alshamsi, A. (2025). *Are Carbon Offsets Fixable?* *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* 50:649–80

⁴ Armstrong McKay, D. I., Staal, A., Abrams, J. F., Winkelmann, R., Sakschewski, B., Loriani, S., & Lenton, T. M. (2022). *Exceeding 1.5 C global warming could trigger multiple climate tipping points.* *Science*, 377(6611), eabn7950.

Open Letter from Scientists: Climate Neutrality Is Europe's Greatest Economic Opportunity

Dear Heads of State and Heads of Government,

We, the undersigned scientists, call on you to support an ambitious EU climate target of minimum 90%–95% net domestic reduction of greenhouse gases (GHG) by 2040 compared to the 1990 level. As shown by the IPCC Synthesis Report 2023 on Climate Change⁵, human activities, principally through emissions of GHG, have been unequivocally driving climate changes including both global warming and extreme events. Global surface temperature has already reached an increase of 1.3°C above 1850-1900 in the smoothed trend, with 2024 even exceeding 1.5°C.⁶ The German Physical Society and the German Meteorological Society recently expressed concerns about global warming accelerating faster than previously expected unless further efforts of greenhouse gas mitigation are made, beyond those that are currently planned.⁷ The prevalence, extent and impacts of extreme weather events has been significantly increasing – also in the EU. Vulnerable communities and regions of the world who have historically contributed the least to current climate change, are disproportionately affected. Scientific work clearly shows that the increase of GHG originates from unsustainable energy use, land use and land-use change, lifestyles and patterns of consumption and production. This has led to widespread adverse impacts on food and water security, human health, ecosystem health, and our economy, increasingly driving losses and damage to people and to biodiversity. Without action, these trends will worsen. Consequently, insurance companies are increasingly refusing to insure buildings and land in critical regions.⁸

As stated by the Council of the European Union and its representatives on multiple occasions at EU and international level, the impacts of climate change affect every continent. Accordingly, sticking to the Paris Agreement is absolutely imperative for securing a safe(r) future compared to all other (worse) scenarios; while the costs and risks of poor action(s) are guaranteed to increase.

⁵ IPCC. (2023). *IPCC Synthesis Report*. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.

<https://www.ipcc.ch/synthesis-report/>

⁶ <https://wmo.int/media/news/wmo-confirms-2024-warmest-year-record-about-155degc-above-pre-industrial-level>

⁷ "Drei-Grad-Grenze könnte schon um 2050 erreicht werden; Klimaanpassung beschleunigen."

https://www.dpg-physik.de/veroeffentlichungen/aktuell/2025/klimaforschende-wenden-sich-an-die-deutsche-politik?set_language=en

⁸ <https://www.allianz.com/de/mediocenter/news/berichte-studien/250724-klimawandel-es-ist-in-unserer-verantwortung-zu-handeln.html>

Recently, EU decision-makers have reaffirmed a commitment to scale up urgent action to address the crises and challenges posed by climate change, biodiversity loss, desertification, ocean and land degradation, drought and pollution^{9,10,11}. Similarly, on the occasion of the 50th anniversary of EU-China diplomatic relations¹², and on the 10th anniversary of the adoption of the Paris Agreement, EU leaders announced they will demonstrate leadership by submitting a 2035 nationally determined contribution (NDC) covering all economic sectors and being in alignment with the Paris Agreement.^{13,14,15}

Scientific analyses show that decarbonization presents substantial opportunities for investment, innovation, and the creation of hundreds of thousands of jobs, while supporting Europe's position in technological leadership¹⁶.

A global transition is underway. Countries around the world are advancing in clean industries, renewable energy, and future markets. Maintaining a consistent trajectory in climate policy is critical for Europe to remain competitive and technologically advanced. Ambitious climate targets are therefore the foundation of Europe's competitiveness. At COP30 in Belém, Europe's level of ambition will signal whether it intends to remain a global leader in climate policy and sustainable industrial innovation, or risks falling behind.

The 2040 carbon reduction target of at least 90–95% is key. The European Climate Law has established climate neutrality by 2050, with a legally binding 55 percent reduction by 2030. Rapid reductions are essential for compliance with climate targets, because climate change depends not on yearly actions, but on cumulative emissions. Scientific models indicate that achieving at least a 90 percent domestic emission reduction by 2040

⁹ Council of the European Union. *Council conclusions on the preparation for COP29*. ST-14459-2024-INIT. Oct. 14, 2024. <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-14459-2024-INIT/en/pdf>

¹⁰ Council of the European Union. *Council conclusions on preparations for COP30*. Nov. 10–21, 2025. <https://cdn.table.media/assets/europe/cop30-council-conclusions.pdf>

¹¹ Council of the European Union. *Conclusions on climate finance in view of the 2024 UN Climate Change Conference, COP29, on 11–22 November 2024*. ST 14288/24. Oct. 8, 2024. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/br0jbgpj/st14288en24.pdf>

¹² Council of the European Union. (2025, July 24). *Joint EU-China press statement on climate: The way forward after the 10th anniversary of the adoption of the Paris Agreement* (Press release No. 638/25) [PDF]. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2025/07/24/joint-eu-china-press-statement-on-climate/>

¹³ Council of the European Union. (2024, November 19). *G20 Rio de Janeiro Leaders' Declaration* [PDF]. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/11hh2mb/g20-rio-de-janeiro-leaders-declaration-final.pdf>

¹⁴ Council of the European Union. (2023, December 1). *Address by President Charles Michel at the UN climate change conference (COP28) in Dubai* [Speech]. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2023/12/01/address-by-president-charles-michel-at-the-un-climate-change-conference-cop28-in-dubai/>

¹⁵ Council of the European Union. (2024, November 12). *Remarks by President Charles Michel at the World Leaders Climate Action Summit in Baku* [Speech]. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/11/12/remarks-by-president-charles-michel-at-the-world-leaders-climate-action-summit-in-baku/>

¹⁶ European Commission. *Staff Working Document SWD(2024) 63 final: Impact Assessment Report – Part 1*. Accompanying the document COM(2024) 63 final. Feb. 6, 2024. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:6c154426-c5a6-11ee-95d9-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF

is necessary to remain on track for net-zero and to comply with the Paris agreement. The advisory opinion of the International Court of Justice stressed the binding character of this agreement and the EU obligation to take the lead in combating climate change by limiting its greenhouse gas emissions¹⁷.

The benefits of such a target are enormous. If done correctly, it could, among others,

- save over **€850 billion** in fossil fuel imports between 2025 and 2040¹⁸,
- increase competitiveness and create more than **2 million new jobs** in clean industries¹⁹,
- **cut household energy bills** by up to two-thirds²⁰, and
- **reduce Europe's dependency on autocratic countries**, strengthening independence and resilience.

The decreasing trends in Europe's natural carbon sink further emphasizes an increasing need to reduce emissions while protecting and restoring the natural sinks – such as forests, peatlands and grasslands – in most member states so that the EU can achieve its climate neutrality goal^{21,22}.

The cost of inaction, by contrast, is substantial: In 2024 alone, an estimated 62,700 premature deaths occurred due to climate-related factors in the EU. Heatwaves, floods, and other extreme weather events continue to cause both economic damage and human suffering. In comparison, additional annual investments required for the transition are approximately 1.5 % of EU GDP, with long-term benefits for resilience, innovation, and prosperity²³.

In summary, scientific evidence clearly demonstrates that an ambitious 2040 climate target is compatible with economic prosperity, technological leadership, and societal well-being. Maintaining a clear trajectory towards climate neutrality supports Europe's competitiveness and ensures that investments in the green transition are effective and timely.

Accordingly, we urge you to stand by your own words and announced actions, and to adopt an ambitious EU climate goal of **90%–95% domestic GHG reduction by 2040**. Europe's future prosperity, safety and well-being depend on the decisions you make today.

¹⁷ International Court of Justice (2025). *Obligations of States in respect of Climate Change*. <https://www.icj-cij.org/case/187>

¹⁸ Strategic Perspectives. (2024). *EU Gas Insight*. <https://strategicperspectives.eu/eu-gas-insight/>

¹⁹ Strategic Perspectives. (2024, April 11). *Forging economic security and cohesion in the EU*. <https://strategicperspectives.eu/report-forging-economic-security-and-cohesion-in-the-eu/>

²⁰ Strategic Perspectives. (2024, April 11). *Forging economic security and cohesion in the EU*. <https://strategicperspectives.eu/report-forging-economic-security-and-cohesion-in-the-eu/>

²¹ Korosuo et al. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13021-023-00234-0>

²² Di Lallo et al. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2023.2273948>

²³ European Commission. (2024, February 6). *Communication on Europe's 2040 climate target and path to climate neutrality by 2050* [Q&A]. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_24_589

Sincerely,

(2178 alphabetically ordered signatories:)

Teresa Abaurrea, M.Sc., University of Helsinki, Finland
Simona Abbà, PhD, National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Italy
Prof. Thomas Abeli, Department of Earth of Environmental Sciences, University of Pavia, Italy
Dr. Maës Abigail, Laboratoire Interdisciplinaire des Environnements Continentaux, Université de Lorraine, France
Dr. Jesse F. Abrams, University of Exeter, UK
Dr. Gian Paolo Accotto, CNR-Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Italy
Rens Accou, Doctoral Researcher at Department of Environment, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Carmen Acedo Departamento de Biodiversidad y Gestión Ambiental (Botánica), Facultad de Ciencias Biológicas y Ambientales, Campus de Vegazana s/n, Universidad de León, León, España
Dr. Hannah Ackermans, University of Bergen, Norway
Dr. Belén Acuña-Míguez, URFM-INRAE, Avignon, France
Balazs Adam, M.Sc., HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Hungary
Dr. Patricia Adame, Spain
Dr. Peter Adamík, Palacky University, Czechia
Prof. Dr. Dominique Adriaens, evolutionary biologist, Ghent University, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Werner Aeschbach, Universität Heidelberg, Germany
Prof. Dr. Göran Ågren, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
Dr. Eduardo Aguilera, Spain
Agustí Agut Escrig, Olarizu Botanical Garden's Curator, Vitoria-Gasteiz City Council, Basque Country, Spain
Dr. Gilbert Ahamer, Environment Agency, Vienna, senior international expert
Univ.-Prof. i. R. Dr. Josef Christian Aigner, Universität Innsbruck, Austria
Diogo Alagador, Biodiversity Research Chair, Mediterranean Institute for the Agriculture, Environment and Development, MED/CHANGE, University Évora, Portugal
Dr. M. Remedios Alarcón Villora, Spain
Dr. Edwin Alblas, Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands
Prof. Dr. Veronika Albrecht-Birkner, Universität Siegen, Germany
Prof. Julio Manuel Alcántara, Universidad de Jaén, Spain
Almut Alexa, M.Sc., German Aerospace Center (DLR) and University of Innsbruck, Germany
Dr. Estrella Alfaro Saiz, University of León. Department of Biodiversity and Environmental Management. Spain
Jun.-Prof. Dr. Djamil Al-Halbouni, University of Leipzig, Germany
Dr. Audrey Alignier, France
Prof. Dr. Stefan Alkier, Goethe Universität Frankfurt am Main, Germany
Clémence Alleman, PhD student, University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne, France
Carlos Alonso Alvarez, Evolutionary Ecology Department, National Museum of Natural Sciences (MNCN-CSIC). Madrid, Spain
Rocío Alonso del Amo, Ecotoxicology of Air Pollution, CIEMAT, Madrid, Spain
Dr. Antonio Alonso Mielgo, Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain
Dr. Maria Alp, RiverLY, AQUA, INRAE, Villeurbanne, France
Dr. Inés Álvarez, Real Jardín Botánico (Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas), Madrid, Spain.
Prof. Pedro Álvarez-Álvarez, University of Oviedo, Spain
Prof. Cristina Amaro da Costa, Department of Ecology and Sustainable Agriculture, School of Agriculture, Polytechnic Institute of Viseu
Simona Amaro, Ph.D. candidate at Maastricht Sustainability Institute, Maastricht, Netherlands
Prof. Ibone Ametzaga Arregi, Department of Plant Biology and Ecology, University of the Basque Country
Dr. Marco Ancrenaz, France
Mina Anders, M.Sc., University of Göttingen, Germany
Dr. Enrique Andivia, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Lucija Andjel, Institute of Animal Physiology and Genetics, Czech Academy of Sciences, Libečov, Czech Republic
Dr. Karl Andraczek, German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig, Germany
Dr. Hampus André, Department of Sustainable Development, Environmental Science and Engineering, Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden
Dr. François Andre, I2BC institute, University Paris-Saclay, Saclay, France
Prof. Dr. Largus Angenent, University of Tübingen, Germany
Csonka Anna Cseperke, M.Sc., HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Hungary

An Ansoms, Université Catholique de Louvain, professor in social sciences
PD Dr. Nils Anthes, University of Tuebingen, Germany
Marc Anton Recasens, Catalan Ornithological Institute (ICO), Barcelona, Spain
Dr. Ioanna Antoniadis, Umeå Plant Science Center, Sweden
Prof. Lucia Aquilanti, Università Politecnica delle Marche, Italy
Prof. Dr. Alexandra Aragão, University of Coimbra Institute for Legal Research, Portugal
Pedro Aragón, Dpto. Biogeografía y Cambio Global, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (CSIC), Madrid, Spain
Alessandro Araldi, Centre for Research into Ecological and Environmental Modelling, University of St Andrews, UK
Dr. Sergio Aranda-Barranco, Department of Ecology, University of Granada, Spain
Prof. Dr. José Pedro Araújo, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, Portugal
Dr. Susanne Arbeiter, Greifswald University, Germany
Dr. Frédéric Archaux, INRAE, France
Prof. Salvador Arenas-Castro, Area of Ecology, Dept. of Botany, Ecology and Plant Physiology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Cordoba (Spain)
Dr. Carlos A. Arias, Aarhus University, Department of Biology, Denmark
Dr. Sophie Armitage, Institute for Biology, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Christine Arncken, Dipl. Ing.-Agr.ETH, Forschungsinstitut für Biologischen Landbau FiBL, Schweiz
Júlia Arraiza Ribera, M.Sc., Vlaams Instituut voor Biotechnologie, Belgium
Joselyn Verónica Arreaga Espin, M.Sc., BOKU University, Institute of Hydrobiology and Aquatic Ecosystem Management, Vienna, Austria
Univ.-Prof. Dr. Enrico Arrigoni, Professor of Theoretical Physics, Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
PhD Marta Arroyo, Institute of Agrochemistry and Food Technology (IATA) - Spanish Research Council, Spain
Adina Arth, M.Sc./PhD candidate, ZHAW School of Management and Law & University of St. Gallen, Switzerland
Sophie Arzberger, M.Sc., Technical University of Munich, Germany
Dr. Sarah Asam, Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR), Germany
Dr. Furqan Asif, Centre for Blue Governance, Aalborg University, Denmark
Dr. Giacomo Assandri, Università del Piemonte Orientale, Alessandria, Italy
Ass.-Prof. Dr. Gerald Auer, University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Harald Auge, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research GmbH – UFZ, Germany
Dr. Julie Augustin, HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Budapest, Hungary
Dr. Matthieu Authier, La Rochelle Université, La Rochelle, France
Pablo Aycart Lazo, Department of Botany and Biodiversity Research, University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria
Dr. Atia Azad, University of Oslo, Norway
Dr. Julien Azuara, Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, Besançon, France
Dr. Javier Babi Almenar, Politecnico di Milano, Italia
Omer Babiker, Ph.D. Student, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway
Dr. Doreen Babin, Julius Kühn Institute (JKI) – Federal Research Centre for Cultivated Plants, Institute for Epidemiology and Pathogen Diagnostics, Braunschweig, Germany
Prof. Dr. Markus Babo, Catholic University of Applied Sciences Munich, Germany
Dr. Ivan Baccelli, National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Italy
Dr. Gabriel Bachner, University of Graz, Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change, Austria
Prof. Antoine Bailleux, UCLouvain, Belgium
Dr. Ir. Mark R Bakker, UMR 1391 ISPA, Bordeaux Sciences Agro – INRAE, F-33140 Villenave d'Ornon, France
Prof. Jan Bakker, University of Groningen, The Netherlands
Dr. Tristan R.M. Bakx, Centre for Research on Ecology and Forestry Applications (CREAF), Cerdanyola del Vallès, Barcelona, Spain
Prof. Viviane Baladi, CNRS (retired) and Mathematics Center Lund University Sweden
Dr. Lola Balaguer-Núñez, Institut d'Estudis Espacials de Catalunya IEEC-ICCUB, Spain
Dr. Juan Antonio Balbuena, Cavanilles Institute of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Biology, University of Valencia, Spain
Prof. András Báldi, HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Hungary
Heikel Balti, Ph.D. student, Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, CNRS, Chrono-environnement (UMR 6249), F-25000 Besançon, France
Eduardo Nuno Barata, Associate Professor, Department of Biology, University of Évora, Évora, Portugal
Dr. Pietro Barbieri, Associate Professor in agronomy, Bordeaux Sciences Agro, INRAE
Sébastien Barot, Institut of Ecology and Environmental Sciences, IRD

2025-10-20: Climate Neutrality is Europe's Greatest Economic Opportunity

Dr. Iestyn Barr, Department of Natural Sciences, Manchester Metropolitan University, UK
Dr. Arnaud Barras, Swiss Ornithological Institute, Switzerland
Pierre Barré, Laboratoire de Géologie de l'ENS, CNRS
Dr. Ceres Barros, University of British Columbia, Canada
Dr. Léonard Barthélemy, Institut des géosciences de l'Environnement, IGE, Grenoble, France
Dr. Alexandra Barthelmes, Senior Scientist, Department of Botany and Landscape Ecology, University Greifswald
(Partner in the Greifswald Mire Center)
Dr. Igor Bartish, Department of Population Ecology, Institute of Botany, Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic
Prof. Marco Bartoli, Parma University, Italy
Dr. Björn Bastian, Wilhelm Ostwald Institute of Physical Chemistry Leipzig, Germany
Prof. Miguel Bastos Araújo / Departamento de Biogeografía y Cambio Global, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, MNCN-CSIC, Spain / Cátedra de Biodiversidade "Rui Nabeiro", Mediterranean Institute for Agriculture, Environment and Development (MED), and Global Change and Sustainability Institute (CHANGE), Universidade de Évora, Portugal
Dr. Flavio Bastos Campos, UFZ Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Germany
Prof. Dr. Ana Bastos, Institute for Earth System Science and Remote Sensing, Leipzig University, Germany
Remy Bataillie, PhD student, Umlp - Besancon, France
Dr. Giorgia Batelli, National Research Council of Italy, Italy
Alessandra Bateman-Neubert, Ph.D. student, Centre for Ecological Research and Forestry Applications, Autonomous University of Barcelona, Spain
Dr. Femke Batsleer, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Mara Baudena, Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate, National Research Council, Turin, Italy
Dr. Gino Baudry, Switzerland
Dr. Amely Bauer, CASUS – Center for Advanced Systems Understanding (HZDR e.V.), Görlitz, Germany & UFZ – Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Halle, Germany
Dr. Markus Bauer, TUM School of Life Sciences, Technische Universität München, Germany
Dr. Dennis Baulechner, Justus Liebig Universität Gießen, Germany
Dr. David Bauman, Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD), Montpellier, France
Dr. Matthias Baumann, Geography Department, Humboldt-University Berlin, Germany
Prof. Dr. Franz Baumann, Georgetown University, Washington D.C., USA
Dr. Pamela Baur, University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Juan Bautista Climent Oliver, Universitat de València
Dr. Susana Bautista, Multidisciplinary Institute for Environmental Studies, University of Alicante, Spain
Dr. Paolo Becciu, Swiss Ornithological Institute, Sempach, Switzerland
Prof. Dr. Frauke Becker, Life Sciences Faculty, Rhine-Waal University, Germany
Prof. Dr. Katrin Bederna, University of Education Ludwigsburg, Germany
Dr. Roland Jan-Reiner Bednarz, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Germany
Beatrice Bednarz, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Germany
Prof. Tom Beeckman, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium
Dr. Matthias Beekmann, Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace, Laboratoire InterUniversitaire des Systèmes Atmosphériques
Dr. Ilka Beil, University of Greifswald, Germany
Norea Beißwenger, B.Sc., University of Tübingen, Germany
Justine Bélik, University of Namur, Belgium
Dr. Xavier Bellanger, Associate Professor, Université de Lorraine, Nancy, France
Assoc. Prof. Salim Belyazid, Department of physical geography, Stockholm University, Sweden
Dr. Raquel Benavides, Department of Natural Systems and Resources, Polytechnic University of Madrid, Spain
Dr. Julian Bender, Chair of Biochemistry II, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Germany
Dr. Thomas Benedikter, Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy
Prof. Dr. Niels Benedikter, University of Milan, Italy
Dr. Sarah Benhaiem, Leibniz Institute for Zoo and Wildlife Research, Berlin, Germany
Dr. Simon Benhamou, Centre d'Ecologie Fonctionnelle et Evolutive, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, France
Dr. Ana Benítez López, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (MNCN-CSIC), Spain

Petra Benyei, Instituto de Economía, Geografía y Demografía, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Spain
Prof. J. Philipp Benz, Technical University of Munich, Germany
Dr. Tristan Berchoux, University of Montpellier, France
Dr. Elisa Berdalet, Institute of Marine Sciences (ICM-CSIC), Spain
Dr. Monica Berdugo, University of Freiburg, Germany
Dr. Christiane Berger, IPG, Goethe-Universität Frankfurt, Germany
Sebastian Berghald, M.Sc., Belgium
Dr. Kolja Bergholz, University of Potsdam, Germany
Nora Bergman, M.Sc., University of Helsinki, Finland
Dr. Joana Bergmann, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Germany
Dr. María Bernechea, Instituto de Nanociencia y Materiales de Aragón (INMA), CSIC-Universidad de Zaragoza
Dr. Thomas Bernet, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture - FiBL, Frick, Switzerland
Dr. Alberto Bernués, Centro de Investigación y Tecnología Agroalimentaria de Aragón (CITA), Spain
Margherita Berri, M.Sc., Wageningen University and Research, Netherlands
em. Univ.-Prof. Erminald Bertel, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Dr. Elsa Berthet, INRAE, France
Dr. Mélissa Berthet, Université de Rennes, France
Dr. Guntram Berti, Hochschule Koblenz, Department of Mathematics, Informatics, Technology, Remagen, Germany
Giacomo Bertoldi, Institute for Alpine Environment, Eurac Research, Bolzano, Italy
Ass.-Prof. Michael Bertram, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
Mélanie Bertrand, Ph.D. student, Centre d'Ecologie Fonctionnelle et Evolutive, Montpellier, France
Dr. Daniel Berveiller, daniel.berveiller@universite-paris-saclay.fr, France
Prof. Aurélien Besnard, Ecole Pratique des Hautes Etudes, Centre d'Ecologie Fonctionnelle et Evolutive, France
Myriam Besson, doctorante, Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace, Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique, Ecole Normale Supérieure, Paris, France
Nele Bettels, University of Rostock, Germany
Prof. Dr. Oliver Betz, University of Tübingen, Germany
Dr. Friderike Beyer, Chair of silviculture, University of Freiburg, Germany
Dr. Matthias Biber, Senckenberg – Leibniz Institution for Biodiversity and Earth System Research, Germany
Prof. Dr. Sabine Bieberstein, KU Eichstätt-Ingolstadt, Germany
Nicolas Bienville, CNRS, Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace, Université Paris Saclay
Antoine Bierjon, Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, Paris, France
Dr. Jelle Bijma, Germany
Dr. Eva Bilkova, Department of Biology and Ecology, University of Ostrava, Czech Republic
Dr. Francoise Binet, CNRS, University of Rennes, France
Dr. Sebastian Birk, Aquatic Ecology, University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany
Anna Biró, M. Sc., Eötvös Loránd University, Department of Systematic Zoology and Ecology, Budapest, Hungary
Prof. Dr. Armin Bischoff, Avignon University, Mediterranean Institute of Biodiversity and Ecology
Dr. Heidi Björklund, University of Helsinki, Finland
Dr. Juan A. Blanco, Head of Ecology and Environment Group, Public University of Navarre, Spain
Assoc Prof. Dr. Niels Blaum, University of Potsdam, Germany
Prof. Mark Blaxter, Tree of Life, Wellcome Sanger Institute, UK
Prof. Dr. Jens Blechert, Universität Salzburg, Austria
Dr. Annick Bleys, Ghent University-VIB, Belgium
Prof. Jan Blieske, Hochschule Wismar, Germany
Svenja Bochinski, M.Sc., Universität Kassel, Germany
Christine Bochynski, Doctoral Researcher, Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology, Ploen, Germany
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Anke Bockreis, Universität Innsbruck, Austria
Dr. Pál Boda, Institute of Aquatic Ecology, HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Vácrátót, Hungary
Philipp Morten Bodien, University of Greifswald, Greifswald, Germany
Dr. Svante Bodin, Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Sweden
Dr. Wout Boerjan, Professor, VIB and Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Laura Boeschoten, Q-ForestLab, Department of Environment, Ghent University, Belgium

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Dr. Fabian Boetzl, University of Würzburg, Germany
Prof. Giuseppe Bogliani, University of Pavia, Italy
Sina Bohm, PhD, Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands
Hannah Böhner, Thünen Institute of Rural Studies, Johann Heinrich von Thünen Institute, Brunswick, Germany
Dr. Lisa Bohunovsky, Zentrum für globalen Wandel und Nachhaltigkeit, BOKU Universität Wien
Dr. Sébastien Boinot, School of Biological Sciences, Queen's University Belfast, UK / Co-Centre for Climate + Biodiversity + Water, Belfast, UK
Yoann Boisson, Ph.D. student, laboratoire Chrono-environnement, Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, Montbéliard, France
Dr. Céline Boisvenue, University of British Columbia, Canada
Lucilla Boito, Ph.D. candidate, Bio-based sustainability engineering, University of Antwerp, Belgium
Dr. Dani Boix, GRECO, Institute of Aquatic Ecology, University of Girona, Spain
Dr. David Bold, Max Planck Institute for Plasma Physics, Germany
Eric Bollinger, University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU), Landau, Germany
Shunko Bolsée, INRAE, France
Dr. Paolo Bonasoni, CNR - ISAC, Italy
Dr. Giulia Bongiorno, Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands
Dr. François Bonhomme, Directeur de recherches émérite, Université de Montpellier, France
Dr. Sandrine Bonhomme, France
Dr. Andrea Bonisoli Alquati, Department of Biological Sciences, California State Polytechnic University – Pomona, Pomona, CA, USA
Dr. Xavier Bonnet CNRS, CEBC UMR 7372, 79360 Villiers en Bois, France
Dr. Timothée Bonnet, Centre d'Etudes Biologiques de Chizé, CNRS - La Rochelle Université, France
Prof. Dr. Dries Bonte, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Coline Boonman, Wageningen University and Research, The Netherlands
Prof. Wiebren Johannes Boonstra, Natural Resources and Sustainable Development, Department of Earth Sciences, Uppsala University, Sweden
Ass. Prof. DI Dr. Florian Borgwardt, BOKU University, Institute of Hydrobiology and Aquatic Ecosystem Management, Vienna, Austria
Prof. Lowe Börjeson, Stockholm University, Sweden
Dr. Frederic Borne, France
Georgia Born-Schmidt, Dipl. Geog., biometrio.earth, Saarbrücken, Germany
Assoc. Prof. Michael Borregaard, Globe Institute, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Dr. Laura Bosco, Finnish Museum of Natural History, Finland
Zoltán Botta-Dukát, HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Hungary
Dr. Katia Bougiouri, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Titouan Bouinier, Collège de France, France, Paris
Dr. Gabrielle Bouleau, UMR LISIS, INRAE, scientific director of PIREN Seine
Dr. ir. Ivo Bouwmans, Lecturer, Delft University of Technology, Delft, The Netherlands
Dr. Heinrich Bovensmann, Institute for Environmental Physics, University Bremen, Germany
Roxane Bradaczek, Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development, University of Göttingen, Germany
Prof. Dr. Corina Bradu, University of Bucharest, Romania
Dr. Mariana Braga, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
Prof. Mattia Brambilla, University of Milan, Italy
Florian Braumann, M.Sc., Hochschule Weihenstephan-Triesdorf, Germany
Alexander Brauser, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany
Broder Breckling, Universität Bremen, Zentrum für Umweltforschung und nachhaltige Technologien (UFT), Leobener Straße 6, D-28334 Bremen
Dr. Benjamin Brede, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Germany
Prof. Dr. Luc Brendonck, Biology Department, University of Leuven (KU Leuven), Belgium
Prof. Damien Brevers, Belgium
Dr. Cameron Brick, University of Amsterdam, Netherlands
Frédéric Briend, Imaging Brain & Neuropsychiatry, Université de Tours, France
Dr. Pina Brinker, University of Regensburg, Germany
Dr. Rose Brinkhoff, Lund University, Sweden

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Prof. Dr. Ulrike Brizay, Catholic University of Applied Science, Berlin, Germany
Dr. Wendy Broadgate, Future Earth, Sweden
Prof. Dr. Thomas Brudermann, University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Aisha Bruendl, Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust, United Kingdom
Prof. Dr. Nicolas Brüggemann, Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany
Dr. Christian Brümmer, Thünen Institute of Climate-Smart Agriculture, Germany
Dr. Stijn Bruneel, Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO), Belgium
Dr. Sophie Brunel-Muguet, Plant Ecophysiology, Unit Research 950 EVA, Inrae, France
Prof. Dr. Pere Brunet, Retired, Polyt. Univ. of Catalonia, Barcelona, Spain
Prof. Gianluca Brunori, Department of Agriculture, Food, and Environment, University of Pisa, Italy
Barbara Brunschweiler, M.Sc., Technical University Munich, Germany
Prof. Dr. Stefan Brunzel, Dept of Biodiversity and Species Conservation, University of Applied Science Erfurt, Germany
Dr. Ursula Bryson, Research Associate at the FitzPatrick Institute of African Ornithology, University of Cape Town, South Africa Sciences
Dr. Ana Buchadas, Earth and Life Institute, UCLouvain, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Bruno Buchberger, Johannes Kepler University, Research Institute for Symbolic Computation, Austria
PD Dr. Solveig Franziska Bucher, Senckenberg Institute for Plant Form and Function Jena, Germany
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Evelyne Buffan-Dubau, University of Toulouse, France
Verena Bühl, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, Switzerland
Dr. Robert Buitenwerf, Center for Ecological Dynamics in a Novel Biosphere (ECONOVO), Department of Biology, Aarhus University, Ny Munkegade 116, DK-8000 Aarhus C, Denmark
Dr. Fabrizio Buldrini, Dipartimento di Bioscienze, Università degli Studi di Milano (Italy)
Prof. Dr. Mirco Bundschuh, University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU), Landau, Germany
PD Dr. Else Bünemann, Forschungsinstitut für Biologischen Landbau, Switzerland
Dr. Allan Buras, Technical University of Munich, Freising, Germany
Hannah Burger, Department of ecology, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
Dr. Jana Bürger, Landscape Ecology, University of Rostock, Germany
József Bürgés, M.Sc., HUN-REN Balaton Limnological Research Institute, Hungary
Dr. Alfred Burian, Umweltforschungszentrum (UFZ), Germany
Dr. Leonard Burtscher, Leiden University, Netherlands
Dr. Michela Busana, Technical University Munich (TUM), Germany
Dr. Henner Busch (Docent), Lund Centre for Sustainability Studies, Lund University, Sweden
Dr. Andrea Busch, Universität Osnabrück, Germany
Dr. Thorsten Busch, ZHAW School of Management and Law & University of St. Gallen, Switzerland
Marc Busuldu Tris, PhD Student in Terrestrial Ecology (Autonomous University of Barcelona), Centre for Ecological Research and Forestry Applications (CREAF), Spain
Marc Busuldu Tris, PhD student, Centre for Ecological Research and Forestry Applications (CREAF), Spain
Lotta Büttel, B.Sc., University of Tuebingen, Germany
Prof. Dr. Tillmann Buttschardt, University of Münster, Germany
Dr. Pauline Buysse, France
David Buysse, Research Institute For Nature and Forest, Brussels, Belgium
Dr. Joan Cáliz, CEAB-CSIC (Spain)
Dr. Carolina Camelo, Institute of Science and Technology Austria, Austria
Dr. Christine Camilleri, France
Ryan Campbell, M.Sc., Anhalt University of Applied Sciences, Germany
Prof. Matteo Campioli, University of Antwerp, Belgium
Dr. David Canal, National Museum of Natural Sciences (MNCN-CSIC), Department of Evolutionary Ecology, Spain
Dr. Elisabetta Canteri, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Beatriz Cantinho, School of Arts, university of Évora, Portugal
Dr. Nuno Capela, Centre for Functional Ecology, University of Coimbra, Portugal
Dr. Paul Caplat, Queen's University Belfast, Belfast, United Kingdom
Dr. Hervé Capra, INRAE, Villeurbanne, France
Carlota Carbajo, PhD student, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Dr. Fabrizio Carbone, CREA Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, Italy

Prof. Damien Cardinal, Laboratoire Océan et Climat Expérimentations et Approches Numériques (LOCEAN-IPSL), Sorbonne Université, Paris

Dr. Jean-François Cardoso, Institut d'Astrophysique de Paris, CNRS

Justine Carey, MSc, Institute of Hydrobiology and Aquatic Ecosystem Management, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), Austria

Dr. Gaetano Caricato, Head of the Terrestrial Ecosystems, Biodiversity, and Land Use Office, Basilicata Regional Environmental Protection Agency (Italy)

Nadia Carluer, Unité de Recherche RiverLy, INRAE Lyon France

Dr. Jofre Carnicer, University of Barcelona, Spain

Prof. Dr. Nils Carqueville, University of Vienna, Austria

Ana Carranco, M.Sc., Universität Ulm, Germany

Dr. Violeta Carrasco, Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria INIA-CSIC, Spain

Alice Carravieri, Centre d'Etudes Biologiques de Chizé, CNRS - La Rochelle Université, France

Assoc. Prof. Dr. João Carvalho, University Trás os Montes and Alto Douro, Portugal

Dr. Giampietro Casasanta, Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate, National Research Council (CNR-ISAC), Italy

Daniele Casella, Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate, National Research Council, Rome, Italy

Dr. Christophe Cassou, CNRS Laboratoire de Meteorologie Dynamique, Paris, France

Dr. Eve Castille, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany

Prof. Jordi Catalan, Spanish Research Council (CSIC). CREA

Dr. Benedetta Catitti, Swiss Ornithological Institute, Switzerland

Dr. Elisa Cavallin, Ghent University, Belgium

Oriol Cayon, Delft University of Technology, The Netherlands

Dr. Marco Cervino, Institute of Atmospheric Science and Climate (ISAC-CNR), Italy

Simone Cescutti, Bielefeld University, Bielefeld, Germany

Dr. Nayden Chakarov, Bielefeld University, Germany

Dr. Simon Chamailé-Jammes, Centre d'Ecologie Fonctionnelle et Evolutive, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, Montpellier, France

Dr. Sylvie Charbit, Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, Institut Pierre Simon Laplace, Université Paris-Saclay

Dr. Rosa M. Chefaoui, Instituto de Investigación en Cambio Global de la Universidad Rey Juan Carlos (IICG-URJC), Spain

Prof. Stefano Chelli, University of Camerino, School of Biosciences and Veterinary Medicine, Camerino, Italy

Dr. Lounes Chikhi, CNRS, University of Toulouse, France

Christophe Chipeaux, M.Sc., Institut National de recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement, Bordeaux, France

Michela Chiumenti, PhD, National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Italy

Dr. Ollivier Chloé, Université de Montpellier, France

Dr. Marta Cholewa, University of Wrocław, Poland

Dr. Pierre Chopin, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Dr. Dr. Jens Christiansen, Lund University Centre for Sustainability Studies, Lund, Sweden

Dr. Papadaki Christina, Institute of Marine Biological Resources and Inland Waters, Hellenic Centre for Marine Research

Prof. Dr. Milan Chytrý, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic

Dr. Fedor Čiampor, Plant Science and Biodiversity Centre, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava, Slovakia

Dr. Alejandro Ciordia, Maastricht Sustainability Institute, Maastricht University, The Netherlands

Dr. Benjamin Claessens, Aix-Marseille University, Marseille, France

Dr. Ana Clara Sampaio Franco, Institute of Aquatic Ecology, University of Girona, Catalonia, Spain

Franziska Clausecker, M. Sc., Grassland Science, University of Göttingen

Dr. Jens Clausen, Borderstep Institut für Innovation und Nachhaltigkeit, Germany

Jimena Clelia López Rivoldi, University of Tübingen, Germany

Dr. Jessica Clement, Researcher, Cirad (UMR CIRED), France

Dr. Floriane Clement, UMR Dynafor, INRAE, France

Arthur Cleyman, Ph.D. Student, VIB-UGent Center for Plant Systems Biology, Ghent University

Prof. An Cliquet, Ghent University, Belgium

J. Mark Cock Ph.D., CNRS, Roscoff Biological Station, France

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Johan Coeck, Research Institute for Nature And Forest, Brussels, Belgium
Dr. Carla Coelho, Lund University, Sweden
Sun Cole Seeberg Dyremose, M.Sc., Aalborg University, Denmark
Federico Colle, Ph.D. candidate, University of Genoa, Cima Foundation, Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (CNR-ISAC) – GE, Italy
Dr. Simon Combes, University College London, UK
Dr. Sébastien Comerón, Universidad de La Laguna, Spain
Dr. Eleonora Cominelli, CNR-Institute of Agricultural Biology and Biotechnology, Italy
Dr. Elena D. Concepción. Forum Basiliense, University of Basel, Switzerland
Dr. Laura Concostrina-Zubiri, IHCantabria - University of Cantabria, Spain
Prof. Gabriella Consonni, Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy
Kasper Coppeters, Q-ForestLab, Department of Environment, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Angela Renata Cordeiro Ortigara, WWF, The Netherlands
Dr. Cristina Corduneanu-Huci, Central European University, Austria
PhD Alban Cornier, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE), France
Prof. Maria Letizia Corradini, School of Science and Technology, Mathematics Division, University of Camerino, Italy
Prof. Emanuela Corsini, Laboratory of Toxicology, Department of Pharmacological and Biomolecular Sciences 'Rodolfo Paoletti', Università degli Studi di Milano, Milano, Italy
Dr. Susanna Corti, National Research Council of Italy - Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate, Italy
Prof. Jordi Cortina-Segarra. Department of Ecology and IMEM. University of Alicante, Alicante, Spain
Prof. Dr. Cristina Amaro Costa, Polytechnic Institute of Viseu, Portugal
PD Dr. Marc Cotter, Research Institute for Organic
Emma Coulembier Vandelannoote, M.Sc., University of Ghent, Belgium
Dr. Aurélie Coulon, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, France
Mariana Couto, M.Sc., Spain
Dr. Camille Coux, France
Prof. Dr. Wolfgang Cramer, Institut Méditerranéen de Biodiversité et d'Ecologie marine et continentale (IMBE), CNRS, Aix-Marseille Université, Aix-en-Provence, France
Thomas Crestey-Chury, Université de Toulouse, France
Janne Creve, University of Graz, Austria
Ewout Crombez, Ph.D. Researcher, Universiteit Gent, Belgium
Beatrice Crona, Professor Sustainability Science, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University
Dr. Agnes Csiszar, Center for Cancer Research, Medical Universita of Vienna, Austria
Prof. Dr. Carin Cuadra, Malmö University, Department of social work, Sweden
Dr. Lucas Czech, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Dr. Jean-Luc Da Lage, UMR 9191 Evolution, génomes, comportement, écologie, CNRS, Gif sur Yvette, France
Linni Dahlhausen, M.Sc., University of Greifswald, Germany
Prof. Dr. Torleif Dahlin, Lund University, Sweden
Dr. Sigrun Dahlin, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Uppsala, Sweden
Dr. Olov Dahlin, University of Gavle, Sweden
Dr. Helmut Dalitz, University of Hohenheim (Stuttgart), Germany
Dr. Martin Dalvai Ragnoli, Institute of Ecology, University of Innsbruck
Dr. Christopher Danek, Alfred-Wegener-Institu, Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung; Universität Bremen, Germany
Dr. Justyna Danielewicz, Department of City and Regional Management, University of Lodz. Poland
Dr. Frederic Danjon, France
Dr. Rutger Dankers, Wageningen University & Research, The Netherlands
Dr. Marie-Claire Danner, Science Officer in European Affairs at the French Foundation for Biodiversity Research, France
Dr. Lipe Renato Dantas Mendes, University College Dublin, Dublin, Ireland
Claudia Danti, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Dr. Jasmin Danzberger, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
Prof. Dr. Marianne Darbi, Hochschule Geisenheim University, Germany
Dr. Avilien Dard, VIB-UGent Center for Plant Systems Biology, Ghent University
Thibault Datry, INRAE, Lyon-Grenoble Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, UR RiverLy, Villeurbanne, Cedex, France

Prof. Dr. Claus-Heinrich Daub, University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland
Prof. Dr. Jacques David, Institut Agro Montpellier, France
Felix David, Soil Biology Wageningen University, The Netherlands & Research Institute of Organic Agriculture, FiBL, Frick, Switzerland
Dr. Eve Davidian, Institut des Sciences de l'Evolution - Montpellier, France
Dr. Silvia De Angeli, LIEC, Université de Lorraine, France
Dr. Laura de Baan, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, Switzerland
Stéphane De Cara, Paris-Saclay Applied Economics, INRAE, AgroParisTech, Université Paris-Saclay
Raphaëlle de Caudron de Coquereaumont, M.Sc., PhD Student, France
Andrea De Cervo, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
Prof. Dr. Olivier De Clerck, Ghent University, Belgium
Laëtitia de Felix, PhD student, Institut National de recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement, UMR ISPA, Bordeaux, France
Janjo de Haan, Wageningen Plant Research, Wageningen University & Research
Prof. Dr. Geert De Jaeger, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Deon de Jager, Globe Institute, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Drs Alfred de Jager, Joint Research Center of the European Commission, Italy
Ir. Ellen De Jonghe, Ghent University, Belgium
Geert De Knijff, senior researcher, Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO), Brussels, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Eduardo de la Peña, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Emiel De Lombaerde, Research Institute for Nature and Forests, Brussels, Belgium
Isabel de Maria C. G. Mourao, Mountain Research Center, Higher School of Agriculture/Polytechnic Institute of Viana do Castelo, Portugal
Prof. Dr. Luc De Meester, Department of Biology, University of Leuven (KU Leuven), Belgium
Dr. Silvia De Monte, CNRS, Institute of Biology of Ecole Normale Supérieure, Paris, France
Prof. Stefaan De Neve, Ghent University, Belgium
Ir. Liselot De Praetere, Ghent University, Belgium
Prof. Raquel de Rivas, PhD, University of Valencia, Spain
Cédric De Smet, PhD student, PSB Departement - VIB and Ghent University, Belgium
Lucia De Stefano, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Dr. Joris de Vente, Spanish Research Council (CSIC), Spain
Ingrid de Vries, B.Sc., Institute of Science and Technology Austria, Austria
Reinier de Vries, M.Sc., Wageningen University & Research, The Netherlands
Prof. Jo De Vrieze, Ghent University, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Ellen Decaestecker, Ecology, Evolution and Biodiversity Conservation, Department of Biology, KULeuven
Kris Decler, M.Sc., Research Institute for Nature and Forest, Belgium
Prof. Wim Declercq, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium
Dr. Marc Deconchat, INRAE, France
Antonia Degen, M.Sc., Thünen Institute of Rural Studies, Germany
Janina Deininger, Greifswald University, Greifswald, Germany
Dr. Louis Delannoy, The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, Stockholm, Sweden
Prof. Dr. Fernanda Delgado, Polytechnic University of Castelo Branco, Portugal
Dr. Nicolas Delhomme, Swedish University for Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
Prof. Dr. Massimo Delledonne, University of Verona, Italy
Dr. Marc Delmotte, Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, Saclay, France
Julien Delord, INSPE, Université de Strasbourg, France
Pr. Nicolas Delpierre, Laboratoire Ecologie, Société, Evolution (ESE), Université Paris-Saclay, France
Dr. Laurence Denaix, UMR ISPA, INRAE, Bordeaux, France
Prof. Dr. Jürgen Dengler, Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW), Wädenswil, Switzerland
Dr. Frantz Depaulis, CNRS-ENS, université PSL, Paris, France
Dr. ir. Leen Depauw, Department of Environment, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, UGent, Belgium
Fabian Deter, M.Sc., Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
Dr. Lisa Deutsch, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
Simon Devin, Université de Lorraine
Prof. Dr. Bart Devreese, Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Edmondo Di Giuseppe, Institute of BioEconomy, National Research Council of Italy

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Dr. Rubén Díaz Sierra, Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED) Spain (Coordinator of the Master's Degree in Climate Change Management)
Prof. Mario Díaz, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Spanish Research Council, Spain
Dr. Emilio Díaz-Varela, University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain
Prof. Jan Diels, Division Soil and Water Management, Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, KU Leuven, Celestijnenlaan 200E, B-3001 Leuven, Belgium
Dr. Dagmar Diesner, Maastricht Sustainability Institute, Maastricht University, The Netherlands
Dr. Roger Dietrich, Germany
Dr. Simon Dietzel, Anhalt University of Applied Sciences, Germany
Dr. Christiana Dietzen, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Prof. Dr. Panayiotis G. Dimitrakopoulos, University of the Aegean, Greece
Dr. Claudia Distler, Ruhr-University Bochum, Germany
Sophia Dobkowitz, M.Sc., Potsdam University, Germany
Prof. Dr. Petra Döll, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany
Prof. J.C. Domec, Bordeaux Sciences Agro, France
Prof. Dr. Michael Domsen, Theologische Fakultät Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg, Germany
Dr. Alexander Donath, Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change (LIB), Bonn, Germany
Prof. Dr. Reik Donner, Hochschule Magdeburg-Stendal, Germany
Dr. Martin Dörenkämper, Fraunhofer Institute for Wind Energy Systems, Germany
Prof. Dr. Wouter Dorigo, Austria
Prof. Dr. Thomas Döring, Institute of Crop Science and Resource Conservation, University of Bonn, Germany
Prof. Dr. Katherine Dormandy, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Prof. Dr. Christian Dorsch, Institute of Geography, Osnabrück University, Osnabrück, Germany
Brian Downes, Ph.D. student, Department of Economics, University of Limerick, Ireland
Sinah Drenske, M.Sc., Leibniz Institute for Zoo and Wildlife Research, Germany
Alexander Drexler, Institut für Botanik und Landschaftsökologie, Universität Greifswald
Dr. Ronald Drimmel, Italy
Prof. Dr. Matthias Drösler, Peatland Science Centre, University of Applied Sciences Weihenstephan-Triesdorf, Germany
Moana Drüe, Ph.D. Student, University of Vienna, Austria
Prof. Filipe Duarte Santos, Faculdade de Ciências, University of Lisbon
Assoc. Prof. Vanessa Duarte, CEFAGE - University of Évora, Portugal
Pierpaolo Duce, National Research Council, Institute of BioEconomy, CNR IBE, Sassari, Italy
Dr. Agnès Ducharne, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, Paris, France, Académie d'Agriculture de France
Dr. Jana Duchoslavová, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Germany
Dr. Simon Dufour, Université Rennes 2 CNRS LETG
Dr. Beatriz Duguy Pedra, Universitat de Barcelona, Spain
Ewout Duhamel, M.Sc., Ghent University, Belgium
Sandra Dullau, Anhalt University of Applied Sciences, Bernburg, Germany
Prof. Dr. Stefan Dullinger, Department of Botany and Biodiversity Research, University of Vienna, Austria
Prof. Dr. Xavier Dumay, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Myriam Dumortier, Ghent University, Belgium
Prof. Dr. John Dunlop, Department of the Chemistry and Physics of Materials, University of Salzburg, Austria
Dr. Guillaume Dupont-Nivet, CNRS - Géosciences Rennes, France
Prof. Dr. Andreas Dür, Department of Political Science, University of Salzburg, Austria
Dr. Arnaud Duranel, France
Prof. Dr. Gabriele Dürbeck, Universität Vechta
Dr. Olivier Duriez, CEFÉ, Univ Montpellier, CNRS, EPHE, IRD, Montpellier, France
Dr. Walter Durka, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research-UFZ, Halle, Germany
Dr. Olivier Dussauge, UCLouvain, Belgium
Igor Eberhard, Mag. Dr., University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Kathrin Eberharter, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Gregory Eckhardt, M.Sc., University of Birmingham, United Kingdom
Prof. Pim Edelaar, Department of Molecular Biology and Biochemical Engineering, University Pablo de Olavide, Sevilla, Spain
Gregory Benjamin Egloff, M.Sc., University of Neuchâtel, Switzerland

Dr. Hartmut Ehmler, Helmholtz Centre for Materials and Energy Berlin (HZB), Germany
Andreas Ehrmann, M.Sc., Institute of Science and Technology Austria, Austria
Nele Eichhorn, B.Sc., University of Oldenburg, Germany
Dr. Laima Eicke, Research Institute for Sustainability, Germany
Dr. Jasper A.J. Eikelboom, Laboratory of Geo-information Science and Remote Sensing, Wageningen University and Research, Netherlands
Prof. Dr. Ulrich L. M. Eisel, University of Groningen, Groningen Institute of Evolutionary Life Sciences, The Netherlands
Prof. Dr. Olaf Eisen, Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung
Prof. Dr. Ute E. Eisen, Universität Gießen, Germany
Dr. Ujala Ejaz, Aarhus University, Denmark
Dr. Elisabeth Ekener, Dept. Sustainable Development, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden
Dr. Sami El Geneidy, University of Jyväskylä, Finland
Dr. Marianne Elias, Institut de Systematique, Evolution, Biodiversité, France
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Isabella Ellinger, Medical University of Vienna, Austria
Assistant Prof. Dr. Thomas Elliot, Aalborg University, Denmark
Dr. Ludger Eltrop, Universität Stuttgart, Institute für Energiewirtschaft und Rationelle Energieanwendung
Prof. Dr. Bernhard Emunds, Phil.-Theol. Hochschule Sankt Georgen, Germany
Theresia Endriss, M.Sc., Technical University of Munich, Germany
Assoc. Prof. Magnuz Engardt, Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, Sweden
Dr. Thore Engel, Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, UFZ – Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research and German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig, Germany
Prof. Dr. Stefanie Engel, Osnabrueck University, Osnabrueck, Germany
Dr. Eva Katharina Engelhardt, Department of Global Change Ecology, University of Würzburg, Germany
Katharina Enigl, M.Sc., GeoSphere Austria, Austria
Dr. Johan Enqvist, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
Rennie Eppenstein, MSc., Research Institute for organic agriculture FiBL, Switzerland
Dr. László Erdős, HUN-REN-DE Functional and Restoration Ecology Research Group, Hungary
Dr. Niclas Ericsson, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
Dr. Markus Eritt, ICOS-FCL @ MPI-BGC, Germany
Dr. Tibor Erős, HUN-REN Balaton Limnological Research Institute, Tihany, Hungary
Prof. Dr. Thomas Ertl, Boku University Vienna, Austria
Rafel Escribano, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain
Dr. Marcial Escudero, Department of Plant Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Biology University of Seville, Spain
Dr. Fabien Esculier, Ecole nationale des ponts et chaussées, France
Dr. Saskia Esselborn, GFZ Helmholtz Center for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Wolfgang Esser-Skala, University of Salzburg, Austria
Univ.-Prof. Dr. Franz Essl, Department of Botany and Biodiversity Research, University Vienna, Austria
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Erik Esterbauer, Mozarteum University Salzburg, Austria
Dr. Laura Estévez Moreno, Departamento de Ciencias Agrarias y del Medio Natural. Universidad de Zaragoza, España.
Prof. Dr. Rampal Etienne, University of Groningen, the Netherlands
Jordan Everall, M.Sc., Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change, University of Graz, Austria
Dr. techn. Manfred Faber, Atominstitut, Techn. Univ. Wien, Österreich
Dr. Adrien Fabre, CNRS and CIRED, Paris, France
Dr. Bruno Fady, Ecology of Mediterranean Forests, INRAE, Avignon, France
Dr. Jakob Fahr, Lower Saxony State Agency for Water Management, Coastal and Nature Conservation (NLWKN), Hannover, Germany
Arne Fahrenholz, University of Greifswald, Germany
Dr. Carsten Falck, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Julia Fält-Nardmann, Professur für Forstzoologie, TU-Dresden, Germany AND Biodiversity Unit, University of Turku, Finland
Dr. Shuya Fan, Department of Botany and Biodiversity Research, University Vienna, Austria
Nicolas Fanin, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE), ISPA lab - BSA
Assistant Prof. Dr. Catherine Farrell, Business and Nature, Trinity Business School, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland.
Asma Fathinejadposhkoohi, Academy of Fine Arts Vienna, Austria

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Dipl. Ing. Philipp Faulhammer, Institute of Biology, University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Lukas Faulstich, Germany
Dr. Roland Faure, Institut Pasteur, France
Dr. Alexander Feckler, Institute for Environmental Sciences, University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU), Landau, Germany
Dr. Katja Fedrowitz, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
Carolin Feimer, Research assistant at Hochschule Anhalt, University of Applied Sciences, Germany
Prof. Dr. Peter H. Feindt, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin
DDr. María Felipe-Lucia, Instituto Pirenaico de Ecología, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Jaca (Huesca), Spain
Prof. Stephanie Feller, Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Germany
Dr. Helen Feord, Postdoctoral researcher, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Stefan W. Ferger, EuroNatur Foundation, Germany
Dr. Marcos Fernández-Martínez, Centre for Ecological Research and Forestry Applications (CREAF), Catalonia, Spain
Dr. Marco Ferrante, University of Göttingen, Germany
Rafaella Ferraz Ziegert, M.Sc., University of Freiburg, Germany
Dr. Ismene Fertschai, University of Graz, Austria, Department of Biology
Fatma Fevzi, M.Sc., Research Institute for Organic Farming (FiBL), Switzerland
Dr. Leonie Fian, University of Graz, Austria
Prof. Dr. Klaus Fichter, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Germany, and Borderstep Institut for Innovation and Sustainability, Berlin
Prof. Dr. Andreas Fichtner, Leuphana University of Lüneburg, Germany
Dr. Sebastian Fiedler, Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
Dr. Jourdain Fievet, Smithsonian Institute, National Museum of Natural History, Washington DC., USA
Prof. Dr. Juliane Filser, University of Bremen & UFT Centre for Environmental Research and Sustainable Technology, Germany
Prof. Dr. Robert Finger, ETH Zürich, Switzerland
Prof. Silvia Fioretti, Università di Urbino, Italy
Kelly Fischer, B.Sc., Vlaams Instituut voor Biotechnologie, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Christina Fischer, Department of Agriculture, Ecotrophology, and Landscape Development, Anhalt University of Applied Sciences, Germany
Prof. Dr. Klaus Fischer, University of Applied Sciences Kaiserslautern, Germany
Prof. Dr. Marina Fischer-Kowalski, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna, Austria
Dr. Cene Fišer, University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Ljubljana, Slovenia
Dr. Wendy Fjellstad, Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO), Norway
Dr. Chris Flechard, France
Máximo Florín, Sección de Humedales, Centro Regional de Estudios del Agua, Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha (Ciudad Real, Spain)
Dr. Timothée Flutre, Quantitative Genetics and Evolution, INRAE
Andreas Focks, Professor for Environmental Systems Modelling, Director of the Research Center for Environmental Systems Research (IUSF), Institute of Mathematics, Osnabrück University, Germany
Prof. Dr. Herbert Formayer, BOKU University Vienna, Austria
Dr. Felix Fornoff, Nature Conservation and Landscape Ecology, University of Freiburg, Germany
Karl-Hermann Förste, B.Sc., University of Greifswald, Germany
Connor Forsyth, Ph.D. candidate at VIB-UGent, Gent, Belgium
Assoc. Prof. Nikolaus Fortelny, University of Salzburg, Austria
Prof. Johannes Foufopoulos, School for Environment and Sustainability, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI
Dr. Julio Fournier, German Environment Agency, Germany
Prof. Hayley Fowler, Newcastle University, UK
Guadalupe Francia, Ph.D., Faculty of Education and Business Studies. University of Gävle, Sweden
Dr. Till Francke, University of Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Thassilo Franke, Bavarian State Collections of Natural History (SNSB) Germany
Dr. Oskar Franklin, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Laxenburg, Austria
Dr. Mathias Franz, Institute for Biology, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Prof. Dr. Martin Franz, Institute of Geography, Osnabrück University

Henning Franzen, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
Prof. Dr. Roberto Franzini Tibaldeo, Pontifical Catholic University of Parana', Brazil
Prof. Dr. Jürgen Freimann, Universität Kassel, Germany, Dep. of Management and Economics
Immanuel Frenzel, Hydrology, Freiburg, Germany
Jana Frenzel, M.Sc., GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Germany
Dr. Lena Frenzke, Post-Doc, University of Technology Dresden Germany, Chair of Botany
Dr. Grégoire Freschet, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, France
Dr. Pascal Frey, INRAE, France
Benoît Fribourg-Blanc, Eng. MSc., Institutional and Technical Support-Cooperation Department, International Office for Water, France
Dr. Hanna Frick, Research Institute for Organic Farming (FiBL), Switzerland
Dr. Julie Friddell, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Germany
Dr. Jonas Friedrich, University of St. Gallen, Switzerland
Dr. Udo Frieß, Institute of Environmental Physics, University of Heidelberg, Heidelberg, Germany
Dr. Friederike Frieß, Institute of Safety and Risk Sciences, BOKU University, Vienna
Dr. Dagmar Frisch, Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (IGB), Berlin, Germany
Prof. Dr. Christine Frison, EcoLAWgy research center, Law Faculty, University of Liège, Belgium
Moritz Peter Fritschle, University of Osnabrück, Germany
Dr. Tobias Froese, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Germany, and Borderstep Institut for Innovation and Sustainability, Berlin
Iven Froese, M.Sc., Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) e.V., Germany
Prof. Nathalie Frogneux, Belgium
Dr. Nathalie Fromin, France
Prof. Dr. Michel Fromm, Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, France
Prof. Dr. Doris Fuchs, University of Münster, Germany
Dr. Heinz Fuchsig, Austrian med. chamber, Sc. lead of Env.health course, MUI (Innsbruck), Austria
Dr. Carina Furusho-Percot, Agroclim INRAE Avignon, France
Dr. Thomas Fuß, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Dr. Catriona Fyffe, Institute of Science and Technology Austria, Austria
Dr. José Luis Gabriel, Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria (INIA-CSIC), Spain
Dr. Tiziana Gaito, Zurich University of Applied Sciences of Business Administration (HWZ), Switzerland
Prof. Dr. Benoit Galand, Belgium
Dr. Hannes Gamper, Amt für Natur und Umwelt, Kanton Graubünden, Switzerland
Dr. Johannes Gantner, Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg, Germany
Dr. Cristina Ganuza, Department of Animal Ecology and Tropical Biology, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Germany
Dr. Iñaki García de Cortázar-Atauri, France
Dr. Pablo García Palacios, Institute of Agricultural Sciences - CSIC, Spain
Dr. João Garcia Rodrigues, CIIMAR, University of Porto, Portugal
Dr. Leo Garcia, Institut Agro, Montpellier, France
Dr. Maxime Garcia, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, Switzerland
Dr. Andrea Garcia, Université catholique de Louvain, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Emili García-Berthou, Institute of Aquatic Ecology, University of Girona, Girona, Catalonia, Spain
Dr. Melissa García-Lamarca, Lund University Centre for Sustainability Studies, Sweden
Dr. Patricia Garnier, INRAE, Université Paris Saclay
Prof. Dr. Claudia Gärtner, Technische Universität Dortmund, Germany
Prof. Dr. Barbara Gasteiger-Klicpera, University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Markus Gastinger, University of Salzburg, Austria
Dr. Veronika Gaube, Institute of Social Ecology, BOKU University, Vienna
Dr. Corentin Gaudichet, UMR Ecobio, Université de Rennes, Rennes, France
Prof. Dr. Ute Gause, Ev.-Theol. Fakultät, Ruhr Universität Bochum, Germany,
Dr. Manon Gautrelet, Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, France
Dr. Aarathy Geetha, University of Salzburg, Austria
Melvin Geib Caballero, University of Kaiserslautern-Landau, Germany
Prof. Dr. Sebastian Geiger, Delft Technical University, Netherlands
Dr. Klaus Peter Geigle, German Aerospace Center, Germany

Dr. Katja Geißler, University of Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Marcos Gektidis, Waldorf School Dietzenbach - Dep. of Biology, Frankfurt, Germany, info@gektidis.de
Dr. Desalegn Chala Gelete, Natural History Museum, University of Oslo,
Dr. Nicole Gervais, University of Groningen, The Netherlands
Dr. Benoît Geslin, Associate Professor, Université de Rennes. Laboratoire Ecobio Fr
Dr. Michael Getzner, Ph.D., Prof., Vienna University of Technology (TU Wien), Department of Public Finance and Infrastructure Policy
Anna L. Geyer, Institute of Political Science, Goethe University Frankfurt am Main, Germany
Prof. Mana Gharun, University of Münster, Germany
Dr. Agneta Ghose, Aalborg University, Denmark
Dr. Lola Gilbert, Centre for Biological Studies of Chizé, La Rochelle Université, La Rochelle, France
Dr. Olivier Gilg, Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, Besançon, France
Prof. Dr. François Gillet, Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, Besançon, France
François Gillet, Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, France
Dr. Mark Gillingham, Max Planck Institute for Biological Intelligence, Department of Ornithology, Eberhard-Gwinner-Strasse 82319 Seewiesen Germany
Dr. Graciela Gil-Romera, Pyrenean Institute of Ecology, Spain
Dr. Tatiana Giraud, CNRS, Laboratoire Ecologie, Société et Evolution (ESE), Université Paris-Saclay
Prof. Giovanni Giuliano, ENEA (retired), Italy
Daniel Glaser, M.Sc., University of Freiburg, Germany
Dr. Anne Glerum, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Germany
Prof. Dr. Christine Globig, Fliedner Fachhochschule Düsseldorf, Germany
Dr. Sebastian Gnann, Chair of Hydrology, University of Freiburg, Germany
Dr. Marta Goberna, Institute of Agriculture and Food Research and Technology - CSIC, Spain
Dr. Olivier Godinot, Institut Agro, Rennes, France
Dr. Diana Goertzen, Technische Universität Braunschweig, Germany
Claude Goeury, retraité CNRS, Marseille, France
Robin Goffaux, project manager, French Foundation for Research on Biodiversity, Paris, France
Sébastien Gogo, scientist, Université de Rennes, Observatoire des sciences de l'environnement de Rennes (OSERen), laboratoire ECOBIO, France
Dr. Alexandra Gogou, Institute of Oceanography, HCMR, Greece
Dr. Isabelle Goldringer, Inrae, Paris-Saclay University, France
Dr. Kelly Gomez-Campo, Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity (HIFMB) / Alfred Wegener Institute for Marine and Polar Research (AWI), Germany
Dr. Pilar Gómez-Ramírez, University of Murcia, Spain
Dr. Luis González Candelas, Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Spain
Dr. Santiago C. González-Martínez, INRAE, Univ. Bordeaux, Cestas, France
Dr. Ursula Görlich, Werne, Germany
Valerie Gössler, B.Sc., University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Brigitte Gottsberger, University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Sarah Gottwald, Leibniz University Hannover, Germany
Dr. Lynn Govaert, Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries, Germany
Prof. Dr. Laura Govers, University of Groningen / NIOZ, Netherlands
Prof. Dr. Wolfgang Goymann, Max Planck Institute for Biological Intelligence, Seewiesen, Germany
Dr. André Tomás Graça, Unit of Structural Biology, EMBL, Grenoble, France
Prof. Dr. Johann Graf Lambsdorff, University of Passau, Germany
Dr. Alexander Graf, Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany
Dr. Marie-Pierre Granger, Central European University, Department of Public Policy, Vienna, Austria
Dr. Hanna Granroth-Wilding, University of Helsinki, Finland
Prof. Dr. Markus Grebenstein, German Aerospace Center, Monash University
Dr. Konstantin Gregor Technical university of Munich, Germany
Ao. Univ.-Prof. Mag. Dr. Irmgard Greilhuber, University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Caroline Greiser, Stockholm University, Sweden
Henny-Catharina Grewe, Scientist, Anhalt University of Applied Sciences, Germany
Christian Griebler, University of Vienna, Department of Functional & Evolutionary Ecology, Austria
Dr. Sarah Griffiths, Department of Natural Sciences, Manchester Metropolitan University, Manchester UK.

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Dr. Angela Grimminger, Paderborn University, Germany
Dr. Hannes Grobe, Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung, Bremerhaven, Germany
Prof. Jean-Emmanuel Groetz, Laboratoire Chrono-Environnement, Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, France
Adrien Grondin, Ph.D. Student, Department of Experimental Psychology, Ghent University
Prof. Dr. Thilo Gross, Germany
Prof. Dr. Hans-Peter Grossart, Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (IGB), Sept. Plankton and Microbial Ecology, Berlin-Steclin, Germany & Potsdam University, Inst. of Biology and Biochemistry, Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Meike Grosse, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL, Frick, Switzerland
Tim Grothey, Borderstep Institute for Innovation and Sustainability and Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Germany
Gabriel Gruber, Dipl.-Ing., BOKU University, Institute of Hydrobiology and Aquatic Ecosystem Management, Vienna, Austria
Dr. Myriam Grundy, France
Dr. Thomas Grünwald, TU Dresden, Germany
Dr. Joanna Grzymała-Moszczyńska, AGH University of Krakow, Poland
Dr. Moisès Guardiola, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain
Prof. Dr. Riccardo Guarino, Department of Biological, Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technologies, University of Palermo, Italy
Dr. Ester Gubi, Department of Global Public Health, Karolinska Institutet, Sweden
Axel Guedj, Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace, Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique, Ecole Polytechnique, CNRS, ingénieur d'étude en sciences atmosphériques
Bertrand Guenet, Laboratoire de Géologie de l'ENS, CNRS
Dr. Guillaume Guérin, France
Prof. Laura Guerrero-Latorre, Faculty of Science, University of Girona, Spain
Dr. Emy Guilbault, University of Helsinki, Research Center for Ecological change, Helsinki, Finland
Antoine Guillaume, CNRS, France
Dr. Joel Guiot, CNRS, Aix-Marseille University, CEREGE, France
Zsófia Eszter Guller, PhD student in Environmental Science, Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences, Hungary
Prof. Dr. Stefan Gumhold, TU Dresden, 01062 Dresden, Germany
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Claudia Gundacker, Medical University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Anke Günther, University of Rostock, Landscape Ecology, Rostock, Germany
Dr. Cordula Gutekunst, Peatland Science, University of Greifswald, Germany
Assoc Prof. Dr. Alba Gutiérrez Girón, PhD, Complutense University, Spain
Dr. Anke Gutmann, Austria
Dr. Valentin Guye, France
Dr. Fanny Guyomarc'h, French National Institute for Agriculture, Food, and Environment (INRAE), France
Dr. Hervé Guyomard, France
Prof. Dr. Gloria Guzmán Casado, Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Spain
Dr. János György, Nagy (PhD, habil). Gödöllő, Egyetem tér 4/a fszt.1, Hungary
Prof. Dr. Peter H.W. Biedermann, Chair of Forest Entomology and Protection, University of Freiburg, Germany
Thomas Haag, PhD student, CNRS, UMR Ecobio, France
Dr. Thomas R. Haaland, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway
Dr. Linda Haaland, Swiss Ornithological Institute, 6204 Sempach, Switzerland
Priv. Doz. DI Dr. phil. Willi Haas, Institute of Social Ecology, BOKU University, Vienna
Dr. Hannah Haberkern, University of Würzburg, Germany
Andreas Haberl, Dipl., Michael Succow Foundation partner in the Greifswald Mire Centre, Germany
Prof. Dr. Helmut Haberl, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), Vienna, Austria
Dr. Gregor Hagedorn, Museum für Naturkunde – Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science, Berlin, Germany
PD Dr. Stefan Hagel, Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austria
Prof. Dr. Anke Hagemann, Habitat Unit and Chair of International Urbanism and Design, Technische Universität Berlin
Prof. Dr. Carmen Hagemeister, Faculty of Psychology, Dresden University of Technology, Germany

Dr. Martin Hagmüller, Graz University of Technology, Austria
Olivier Hagolle, M.Sc., France
Dr. Thomas Hahn, Stockholm University, Sweden
Alexandra Halbleib, B.Sc., Freie Universität Berlin, Institute for Biology, Berlin, Germany
Dr. Moritz Hallama, University of Girona, Spain
Prof. Dr. Lucyna Hałupka, University of Wrocław, Poland
Dr. Bettina Hamann, Technical University Berlin, Germany
Dr. Samuel Hammer, Heidelberg University, Germany
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Edith Hammer, Lund University, Sweden
Dr. Arndt Hampe, UMR1202 BIOGECO, INRAE, France
Dr. Susanne Hanger-Kopp, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Austria
Ira Hannappel, Agroecology & Functional Agrobiodiversity, University of Göttingen, Göttingen, Germany
Dr. Micha Hannich, Institut für Botanik und Landschaftsökologie, Universität Greifswald, Germany
Dr. Jari Hänninen, University of Turku, Finland
PD Mag. Dr. Elisabeth Haring, Natural History Museum Vienna, Austria
Prof. Dr. Wolfgang Harneit, Universität Osnabrück, Germany
Morgan Eleanor Harris, Università degli Studi Roma Tre
Maximilian Hartinger, Germany
Dr. Markus Hartl, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Dr. Margarita Hartlieb, Technische Universität Darmstadt, Germany
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Ute Hasenöhrl, History, University of Innsbruck
Dr. Moshira Hassan, Reef Check e.V. Germany, Germany
Prof. Dr. Martin Hasslmann, University of Hohenheim, Germany
Prof. Dr. Bernhard Haubold, Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology, Plön, Germany
Prof. Dr. Judith Hauck, Alfred-Wegener-Institut, Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung; Universität Bremen, Germany
Johannes Hausharter, Department of Botany and Biodiversity Research, University of Vienna, Austria
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Daniel Hausknost, WU Vienna University of Economics and Business, Austria
Dr. Yann Hautier, Ecology and Biodiversity Group, Department of Biology, Utrecht University, Utrecht, Netherlands
Dr. Alexander Haverkamp, Wageningen University & Research, The Netherlands
Dr. Adam Hearn, University of Basel, Switzerland
Johanna Heck, B.Sc., Landscape Ecology and Nature Conservation, Greifswald University
Prof. Dr. Katrin Heer, Forest Genetics, Albert-Ludwigs Universität Freiburg, Germany
Prof. Dr. Alexandre Heeren, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Petra Heffeter, Medical University of Vienna, Austria, Austria
Prof. Hans-Christian Hege, Zuse Institute Berlin (ZIB), Germany
Prof. Dr. Tina Heger, Technical University of Munich, TUM School of Life Sciences, Freising, Germany
Dr. Lea Heidrich, Department of Geography, University of Marburg
Prof. Dr. Stefan Heiland, Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
Univ. Prof. Dr. Thomas Hein, Institute of Hydrobiology and Aquatic Ecosystem Management, BOKU University, Vienna, Austria
Dr. Charlotte Heinrich, Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt, Germany
Dr. Georg Heiss, Reef Check e.V. Germany, Germany
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Christoph Helbig, University of Bayreuth, Germany
Magdalena Held, Institute for Atmospheric and Earth System Research, University of Helsinki, Finland
Dr. Dupont Hélène, Centre d'Ecologie et des Sciences de la Conservation, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France
apl. Prof. Nadja Hellmann, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität, Mainz, Germany
Dr. Niels Hellwig, Department of Agriculture, Ecotrophology, and Landscape Development, Anhalt University of Applied Sciences
Prof. Dr. Barbara Helm, Swiss Ornithological Institute, Switzerland
Dr. Lia Hemerik, Biometris, Wageningen University, Wageningen, The Netherlands
Dr. Elisabeth V. Henn, Department Nature Conservation & Social-Ecological Systems, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Germany
Dr. Justus Hennecke, Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands
Karl-Martin Hentschel, Dipl. Math., Autor Handbuch Klimaschutz, Heikendorf, Germany

Dr. Jörn Hentschel, Senckenberg Institute for Plant Form and Function Jena (SIP), Herbarium Haussknecht (JE) at Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Germany
Prof. Tomas Herben, Department of Botany, Charles University Praha, Czech Republic
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Ruth Herbst, Medical University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Héctor Hernández Alonso, Centre d'Ecologie Fonctionnelle et Evolutive, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, France
Dr. Eva Hernández Plaza, Institute of Agriculture and Food Research and Technology - CSIC, Spain
Dr. Nuria Hernández-Mora, Universidad Complutense de Madrid and Fundación Nueva Cultura del Agua, Spain
Univ.-Prof. Dr. Gerhard J. Herndl, Dept. Functional and Evolutionary Ecology, University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Ximena Herrera Alvarez, Researcher, Public University of Navarre, Spain
Larissa Zoe Herrmann, Ph.D. Student, RPTU Kaiserslautern-Landau, Germany
Dr. Moritz Hertel, Max-Planck-Institute for biological Intelligence, 82319 Seewiesen, Germany
Dr. Julia Hertin, German Advisory Council on the Environment, Germany
Dr. Laura Herzog, Institute of Geography, Osnabrück University, Osnabrück, Germany
Moritz Heß, M. Ed., University of Kaiserslautern Landau, Germany
Dr. Rudi Hessel, Wageningen Environmental Research (WENR), Wageningen, Netherlands
Dr. Katja Heubach, Palmengarten Frankfurt, Germany
Dr. Holger Heuer, Julius Kühn Institute (JKI) – Federal Research Centre for Cultivated Plants, Braunschweig, Germany
Eileen Heyer M.Sc., Ecological Research Unit, Swiss Ornithological Institute, Sempach, Switzerland
Dr. Thomas Hickmann, Lund University, Sweden
Prof. Dr. Thomas Hieke, Katholisch-Theologische Fakultät, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz, Germany
Dr. med. Dipl. Ing. Rüdiger Hildebrandt, Bonn, Germany
Dr. Rüdiger Hildebrandt, Germany
Prof. Helmut Hillebrand, Institute for Chemistry and Biology of the Marine Environment, University Oldenburg, Germany
Dr. Stephan Hiller, Carl Zeiss Microscopy, Oberkochen
Dr. Sabine Hilt, Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries, Berlin, Germany
Dr. Ralph Hintemann, Borderstep Institute for Innovation and Sustainability, Berlin, Germany
Dr. Sara Hintze, BOKU University Vienna, Austria
Jessica Hintze, University of Greifswald, Greifswald, Germany
Dr. Tjorven Hinzke, University of Greifswald and Helmholtz Institute for One Health, Greifswald
Hannah Hirschmann, University of Greifswald, Germany
Dr. Long Ho. Faculty of Bioscience Engineering. Ghent University. Ghent. Belgium
Dr. Selwyn Hoeks, Radboud University, Nijmegen, the Netherlands
Prof. Dr. Christian Hof, Chair of Global Change Ecology, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Germany
Dr. Benjamin Hofbauer, Research Institute for Sustainability at GFZ, Germany
Dr. Felix Hoffstaedter, Forschungszentrum Jülich
Dr. Alexander Hogrebe, Biochemical data scientist, Germany
Dr. Annette Hohenberger, Institute of Cognitive Science, University of Osnabrueck, Germany
Monika Hohlbein, University of Greifswald and Greifswald Mire Centre, Greifswald, Germany
Prof. Dr. Dirk Hohm, Ostfalia University of Applied Sciences, Germany
Franziska Höhne, M.Sc., Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany
Eva Holländer, Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology, Germany
Dr. Christos Hollerung, University of the Aegean, Greece
Dr. Jutta Holst, Lund University - ICOS Sweden, Sweden
Prof. Joost Holthuis, Center for Cellular Nanoanalytics Osnabrueck, Osnabrueck University, Germany
Dr. Stefan Holzheu, Universität Bayreuth, Germany
Dr. Robert Home, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick Switzerland
Dr. Jürgen Homeier, University of Marburg, Germany
Dr. Oliver Höner, Leibniz Institute for Zoo and Wildlife Research, Berlin, Germany
Dr. Jacqueline Hoppenreijts, Ruhr University Bochum, Germany
Dr. Anja Hörger, University of Salzburg, Austria
Dr. Laura Horn, Roskilde University, Denmark
Julian Hörndl, M.Sc., Universität Salzburg, Austria
Prof. Joaquín Hortal, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (CSIC), Madrid, Spain.

Dr. Zsófia Horvath, HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Hungary
Dr.in Gabriele Hösche-Schagar, University College of Christian Churches of Teacher Education Vienna/Lower Austria, Austria
Konstantin Houbak, M.Sc., Aalborg University, Denmark
Dr. Adrien Houge, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Prof. Dr. Stephan Höyng, Katholische Hochschule für Sozialwesen Berlin, Germany
Bernd Hrdy, DI, BOKU University, Institute for Safety and Risk Sciences, Vienna, Austria
PD Dr. Markus Huber, Justus Liebig University Giessen, Germany
Dr. Evelyne Hübscher, Department of Public Policy, Central European University, Vienna, Austria
Maria Hudl, Institut für Architektur Technische Universität Berlin, Deutschland
Dr. Kévin Huguet (MCF - Lecturer) LCPME Environmental microbiology team, Université de Lorraine, France
Prof. Dr. Lisa Hülsmann, University of Bayreuth, Germany
Amelie Hünnebeck-Wells, Greifswald Mire Centre, Germany
Dr. Louis Hunninck, Swiss Ornithological Institute, 6204 Sempach, Switzerland
Dr. Guido Hunze, University of Münster, Germany
Dr. Daniel Huppmann, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA)
Dr. Vytas Huth, Peatland Science, University of Greifswald, Germany
Assoc. Prof. Hans-Peter Hutter, Medical University of Vienna, Austria
Elise Huysman, Q-ForestLab, Department of Environment, Ghent University, Belgium
Visiting Professor, Professor Emeritus Håkan Hytteborn, Department of plant ecology and evolution, Uppsala University
Dr. Carles Ibáñez, Climate Resilience Centre, EURECAT - Technology Centre of Catalonia, Spain
Prof. José Ignacio Querejeta, Spanish National Research Council (CEBAS-CSIC), Murcia, Spain
Dr. Daniel Imbert, Université des Antilles (FWI university), France
Research Prof. Gwenaél Imfeld, CNRS France
Dr. Stephan Imhof, Biodiversity of Plants, Philipps-Universität Marburg
Dr. Simona Imperio, Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA), Italy
Univ.Prof. em. Heribert Insam, PhD, BioTreat GmbH Innsbruck, Austria
Dr. Katja Irob, The Robert H. Smith Institute of Plant Sciences and Genetics in Agriculture, Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Israel
Dr. Hanna Isaksson, Department of Ecology, Germany
Dr. Jana Isanta-Navarro, Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Qutbudin Ishanch, Ph.D. candidate at Geo- and Environmental Research Center (GUZ), Universität Tübingen, Germany
Md Rafikul Islam, M.Sc., Lund University, Sweden
Dr. José L. J. Ledesma, National Museum of Natural Sciences, Spanish National Research Council (MNCN-CSIC), Spain and Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ), Germany
Prof. Maria J.I. Briones, University of Vigo, Spain
Dr. Kim Jaatinen, Finnish Environment Institute, Finland
Mónika Jablonszky, Ph.D., HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Budapest, Hungary
Dr. Jennie Jackson, University of Gävle, Gävle
Dr. Staffan Jacob, Theoretical and Experimental Ecology Station, UAR2029 CNRS, Moulis, France
Alexander Jacobsen, Doctoral Researcher, Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology, Plön, Germany
Dr. Klaus Jäger, Biochemiker im Ruhestand
Prof. FH I.R. Dr. Dr. h.c. Alexander Jäger, FH Oberösterreich, Austria
Ass.-Prof. Dr. Sarah Jäger, Friedrich-Schiller-University Jena, Germany
Niklas Jaggy, M.Sc., Department of Remote Sensing, Institute of Geography and Geology, University of Würzburg, Germany
FH-Prof. Dr. techn. Dipl.-Ing. Stefan Jaksch, FH Oberösterreich, Austria
Tom Jamonneau, Ph.D. student, CNRS, University of Toulouse, France
Dr. Kateřina Jandová, Charles University, Czechia
Dr. Ute Jandt, Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Halle, Germany
Dr. Serge Janicot, Sorbonne Université
Dr. Monika Janišová, Institute of Botany, Plant Science and Biodiversity Center, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Banská Bystrica, Slovakia
Dr. Noémie Janot, INRAE, Bordeaux, France

Prof. Dr. Florian Jansen, Landscape Ecology, University of Rostock, Germany
Prof. Dr. Ludger Jansen, PTH Brixen College, Bressanone, Italy
Prof. Dr. Patrick Jansen, Utrecht University, Netherlands
Andreas Janßen, Johann Heinrich von Thünen-Institut, Braunschweig, Germany
Dr. Petr Janšta, Department of Zoology, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic
Dr. Andrea Jany, Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change, University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Kamil Jaron, Tree of Life, Wellcome Sanger Institute, UK
Renaud Jaunatre, INRAE, LESSEM, Grenoble, France
Dr. Coline Jaworski, INRAE, France
Dr. Marion Jay, University of Göttingen, Department for agricultural economics and rural development, Germany
Dr. Kévin Jean, Institut de Biologie de l'École Normale Supérieure, Paris Sciences & Lettre, France
Laurent Jeanneau, UMR Géosciences Rennes, CNRS, Rennes, France
Barbara Jechsmayr, MSc., Institute of Ecology, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Prof. Dr. Eckhard Jedicke, Hochschule Geisenheim University, Germany
Dr. Mirjam Jekel, Leibniz Universität Hannover, Germany
Dr. Alienor Jeliaskov, INRAE, UR HYCAR, France
Prof. Dr. Florian Jeltsch, University of Potsdam, Plant Ecology and Nature Conservation
Prof. Anita Jemec Kokalj, University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical faculty
Dr. Laura Jensen, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Germany
Pia Jensen, Ph.D. student, Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development, University of Göttingen (Germany)
Dr. Jens Jetzkowitz, Faculty for Social Sciences and Humanities, Helmut Schmidt University
Arzhvaël Jeusset, PatriNat (OFB-MNHN-CNRS-IRD), France
Prof. Dr. Ostheimer Jochen, Augsburg University, Germany
Prof. Dr. Malte Jochum, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Germany
Janna Jokela, Finland Futures Research Center, University of Turku, Finland
Leonie Jonas, M.Sc., University of Turku, Finland
Dr. Martin Jones, Manchester Metropolitan University, UK
Amanda Jonsson, M.Sc., Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
Prof. Dr. Dr. h.c. Hans Joosten, Greifswald University, Germany
Prof. Dr. Somya Joshi, Docent, Stockholm University, Sweden
Ombeline Jouet, PhD student, Alfred-Wegener-Institut, Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung; Universität Bremen, Germany
Dr. Jean Jouzel, LSCE/IPSL CEA Saclay, 91190, Gif/yvette, France
Irene Julián-Posada, PhD student, Pyrenean Institute of Ecology, Spain
Arthur Jumaucourt, PhD student in Géosciences Rennes, Université de Rennes, France,
Dr. Martin Jung, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Austria
Prof. Dr. Gerald Jurasinski, University of Greifswald, Germany
Dr. Helen Kaberi, Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Greece
Patrick Kacic, M.Sc., Department of Remote Sensing, Institute of Geography and Geology, University of Würzburg, Germany
Patrick Kacic, Ph.D. Student, University of Wuerzburg and German Aerospace Center (DLR)
Tomáš Kadlec, Czech University of Life Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic
Jos Käfer, Institut des Sciences de l'Evolution de Montpellier, Université de Montpellier - CNRS - IRD, France
Prof. Dr. Anne Käfer, Universität Münster, Germany
Angelika Kaffrell-Lindahl, MA, Mid Sweden University, Sweden
Dr. Remi Kahane, France
Rémi Kahane, Research Unit HortSys, CIRAD Montpellier, France
Dr. Lisa Juliane Kahl, Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Germany
Dr. Maria Kahlert, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Uppsala, Sweden
Dr. Martin Kainz, Prof., University for Continuing Education Krems and WasserCluster Lunz, Austria
Prof. Dr. Ulrike Kaiser, Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena
Dr. Tobias Kaiser, Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology, Plön, Germany
Moritz Kaiser, Michael Succow Foundation, Germany
Dr. Petros Kakouros, National Museum of Natural History Goulandris, Greece
Dr. Elfriede Kalcher-Sommersguter, University of Graz, Austria

Dr. Gregor Kalinkat, Leibniz-Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries, Germany
Dr. Gwenaël Kaminski, Université de Toulouse, France
Elias Kapitany, M.Sc., University of Vienna, Austria
Prof. Dr. Florian Kapmeier, ESB Business School, Reutlingen University, Germany
Dr. Ioannis Karaouzas, Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Anavyssos, Greece
Dr. James Karimi, Italy
Dr. Katrin Karner, BOKU University, Austria
Dr. Panagiotis Kasapidis, Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR), Crete, Greece
Katharina Kasper, Mammal Research Institute, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland
Prof. Georgios Katsaros, Institute of Science and Technology Austria, Austria
Daniel Katzlberger, MSc, Digital and Analytical Sciences, University of Salzburg (PLUS), Austria
Dr. Vandana Kaushal, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Dr. Carmen Kayan, Research Institute for Organic Agriculture FiBL, Switzerland
Jule Kegel, M.A., University of Vienna, Austria
Amelie Keller, B.Sc., University of Tübingen, Germany
Dr. Heiko Keller, ifeu – Institut für Energie- und Umweltforschung Heidelberg, Germany
Dr. Julia Kelly, Lund University, Sweden
Assoc. Prof. Steve Kennedy, Erasmus University, Netherlands
Prof. Dr. Lukas Kenner, Medical University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Dorothee Keppler, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Janika Kerner, Postdoc, University of Würzburg, Germany
Dr. Melina Kerou, University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Matthew Kerr, Aarhus University, Denmark
Prof. Dr. Ferdinand Kerschner, Austria
Prof. Dr. Sven Kerzenmacher, University of Bremen & UFT Centre for Environmental Research and Sustainable Technology, Germany
Prof. Dr. Marion Keuchen, Universität Paderborn, Institut für Evangelische Theologie, Germany
Dr. Christoph Keuschnig, Section for Interface Geochemistry, GFZ Helmholtz Center for Geoscience, Potsdam, Germany
Prof. Dr. Kathrin Kiehl, Osnabrück University of Applied Sciences, Germany
Prof. Dr. Klaus Kießling, Philosophisch-Theologische Hochschule Sankt Georgen, Frankfurt
Dr. Minsu Kim, University of Graz, Holteigasse 6, 8010 Graz, Austria
Prof. Dr. Gottfried Kirchengast, Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change & Institute of Physics, University of Graz, Graz, Austria
Dr. Mathias Kirchner, BOKU University, Austria
Prof. Florian Kirfel, Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
Prof. Dr. Anita Kirmer, Anhalt University of Applied Sciences, Germany
Tom Kirschey, Kompetenzzentrum Natürlicher Klimaschutz (KNK), Berlin/Bonn, Germany
Dr. Veronika Kiss, GreenFormation, Budapest
Steffen Kittlaus, Dipl. Geoökol., TU Wien – Institute for water quality and resource management, Vienna, Austria
Niklas H. Kitzmann, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Germany
Prof. Dr. Thanasis Kizos, University of the Aegean, Greece
Dipl.-Ing. Dr. Lukas Daniel Klausner, University of Applied Sciences St. Pölten, Austria
Dr. Lukas Daniel Klausner, University of Applied Sciences St. Pölten, St. Pölten, Austria
Dr. Janina Kleemann, Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Halle (Saale), Germany
Prof. Dr. David Kleijn, Plant Ecology and Nature Conservation GRoup, Wageningen University, Wageningen, the Netherlands
Dr. Clemens Kleinspehn, University of Greifswald, Germany
Prof. Dr. Silja Klepp, Department of Geography, Kiel University
Prof. Jitka Klimešová, Institute of Botany, Czech Academy of Sciences, Czechia
Prof. Dr. Natascha Kljun, Lund University, Sweden
Prof. Dr. Carola Klöck, Centre for International Research (CERI), Sciences P
Dr. Barbara Klotz, Medical University Innsbruck, Austria
Dr. Alena Klvaňová, European Bird Census Council, Czech Society for Ornithology, Prague, Czechia
Assoc. Prof. Michal Knapp, Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Czech Republic

Dr. Sonja Knapp, Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Germany
Dipl.-Ing. Julika Knapp, Universität Innsbruck, Austria
Prof. Dr. Peter Knippertz, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany
Dr. Nina Knittel, University of Graz, Austria
Prof. Dr. Christoph Knoblauch, Pädagogische Hochschule Ludwigsburg, Germany
Prof. Dr. Alexander Knohl, University of Göttingen, Germany
Thomas Knura, Aquatic ecology, University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany
Dr. Larissa Koch, Institute of Geography & Institute of Environmental Systems Research, Osnabrück University, Germany
Prof. Dr. Monika Koch-Müller, Helmholtz Centre Potsdam, GFZ, Germany
Prof. Dr. Heinz Köhler, University of Tübingen, Germany
Daniel Köhn, Botany and Landscape Ecology, University of Greifswald, Germany
Sien Kok, Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands
Aleksandra Kolanek, MSc, Assistant Lecturer/Researcher at University of Wrocław, Faculty of Earth Sciences and Environmental Management (Poland), President of NATRIX Herpetological Association (Poland)
Dr. Peter Koncz, HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Hungary
Assoz. Prof. Mag. Dr. Christine Konecny, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Inga Konecny, DPhil, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria
Dr. Heino Konrad, Austrian Research Centre for Forests (BFW), Vienna, Austria
PD Dr. Dr. Wilfried Konrad, University of Tübingen, Germany
Elisabeth Kopp, M.Sc., Austrian Zoological-Botanical Society, Austria
Dr. Florentine Koppenborg, Technische Universität München, Germany
Dr. Ondřej Korábek, Charles University, Prague, Czechia
Prof. Dr. Robert Kordts, University of Bergen, Norway
Dr. Lotte Korell, Helmholtz-Center for Environmental Research – UFZ, Halle (Saale), Germany
Severin Korfhage, M.Sc., Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity (HIFMB) / Alfred Wegener Institute for Marine and Polar Research (AWI), Germany
Dr. Urs G. Kormann, Swiss Ornithological Institute Sempach, Switzerland
Prof. (Asst) Teea Kortetmäki, Department of Social Sciences and Philosophy, University of Jyväskylä, Finland
Dr. Lutz Kosack, Institut für Agrarökologie und ökologischen Landbau, Universität Bonn
Prof. Dr. Christian Kost, Osnabrück University, Germany.
Prof. Dr. Gertjan Koster, University of Twente, The Netherlands
Prof. Janne Kotiaho, University of Jyväskylä, Finland
Dr. Georgios Kotoulas, Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Greece
Dr. Anikó Kovács-Hostyánszki, HUN REN Centre for Ecological Research, Hungary
Dr. Vienna Kowalik, Freiburg University, Germany
Dr. Krystyna Koziol, Faculty of Geographical Sciences, Kazimierz Wielki University in Bydgoszcz, Poland
Dr. Oleksiy Kozlov, Heidelberg Institute for Theoretical Studies (HITS gGmbH), Germany
Dr. Yvan Kraepiel, Sorbonne Université, France
Prof. Dr. Rüdiger Krahe, Institute of Biology, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
Dr. Viktória Krajanová, Slovak National Museum - Natural History Museum, Bratislava, Slovakia
Marleen Krämer, Ph.D. candidate at the Department of Crop Science, Georg-August-University of Göttingen, Germany
Dr. Maike Krauss, Forschungsinstitut für biologischen Landbau (FiBL), Frick, Switzerland
Prof. Dr. Stefan Krauter, Theologische und Religionswissenschaftliche Fakultät, Universität Zürich, Schweiz
Prof. Dr. Andreas Krebs, Alt-Katholisches Seminar, Universität Bonn, Germany
Prof. Ruth Krebs, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Holger Kreft, University of Göttingen, Germany
Dr. Heidi Kreibich, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Jeppe Kristensen, Aarhus University, Denmark
Dr. Julia Krohmer, Senckenberg Gesellschaft für Naturforschung, Germany
Prof. Kris Krois, Eco-Social Design, Free University of Bozen–Bolzano, Italy
Prof. Dr. Wolfgang Kromp, BOKU University Vienna, Austria
Prof. em. Dr. Dr.hc Helga Kromp-Kolb, BOKU University Vienna, Austria
Andrea Krüger, University of Greifswald, Greifswald, Germany
Jenny Kruttschinna, Reef Check e.V. Germany, Germany

Kenneth Kuba, MSc., Technical University of Munich (TUM), Germany
Prof. Dr. Johannes Kuchler, Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
Prof. Tobias Kuemmerle, Humboldt-University Berlin
Dr. Jonas Kuhn, Department of Atmospheric and Oceanic Sciences, University of California, Los Angeles, USA
Prof. Dr. Ingolf Kühn, Helmholtz Centr for Environmental Research, UFZ & Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Halle, Germany
Lukas Kuhn, PhD, Leuphana University Lüneburg, Germany
Prof. Kalevi Kull, Department of Semiotics, University of Tartu, Estonia
Kayoko Kumasaka, M.Sc., The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, Japan
Prof. Dr. Martina Kumlehn, Universität Rostock, Theologische Fakultät, Germany
Dr. Radek Kundt, Department for the Study of Religions, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic
Dr. Eva Kundtová Klocová, Masaryk University, Czech Republic
Dr. Jan Kunnas, University of Eastern Finland, Finland
Dr. Ralf Kurvers, MPI for Human Development, Germany
Dr. Christoph Kurze, University of Regensburg, Germany
Prof. Dr. Kathrin S. Kürzinger, Evangelische Akademie im Rheinland, Deutschland
Dr. Mieke Kuschnerus, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Germany
Dr. Eliška Kuťáková, Department of Forest Ecology and Management, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Umeå, Sweden
Prof. Thomas W. Kuyper, Wageningen University
Dr. Valentina La Morgia, Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA), Rome, Italy
Prof. Pierrick Labbé, Institut des Sciences de l'Evolution de Montpellier, Université de Montpellier
Dr. Susanne Lachmuth, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg, Germany
Johannes Lackner, M. Sc., University of Würzburg, Germany
Dr. Vincent Lacroix, Biometry and Evolutionary Biology, University Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France
Dr. Florian Ladstädter, University of Graz, Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change, Austria
Dr. Tristan Lafont Rapnouil, Institut de Recherche en Horticulture et Semences (IRHS), INRAE, France
Dr. Sebastien Lafont, France
Alexandra-Ntea Lagki, Ghent University
Dr. Dimitri Lague, CNRS / University of Rennes, France
Dr. Jens N. Lallensack, Germany
Dr. Quentin Lambert, University of Caen Normandy, France
Dr. Carla Lambertini, Università degli Studi di Milano, Department of Biosciences, Italy
Univ.-Prof. Dr. Claus Lamm, University of Vienna and Austrian Academy of Sciences
Prof. Dr. Gerhard Lammel, Max Planck Institute for Chemistry, Mainz, Germany, and Masaryk University, Faculty of Sciences, Brno, Czech Republic
Leni Lammens, Ghent University, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Peter Lampe, Universität Heidelberg
Dr. Christian Lampei, University of Marburg, Germany
Jan Landert, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, Switzerland
Dr. Dries Landuyt, Ghent University, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Christine Lang, Institute for Geography, Osnabrueck University, Germany
Annemarie Lang, M.Sc., University of Tübingen, Germany
Prof. Dr. Holger Lange, Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO), Norway
Dr. Robert Langner, Heinrich-Heine-Universität Düsseldorf, Germany
Anna Lanteri, Doctoral Researcher, German Aerospace Center (DLR), Germany
Isabelle Lanzrein, M.Sc., Technical University of Munich, Germany
Dr. Carlos Lara Romero, Global Change Research Institute at Universidad Rey Juan Carlos (IICG.URJC), Spain
Pr. Catherine Laroche Dupraz, L'Institut Agro Rennes-Angers, France
Dr. Ella Lattenkamp, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Dr. Jörn Lauterjung, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Cormac Lawler, Manchester Metropolitan University, UK
Dr. Colin Lawton, Zoology, School of Natural Sciences, University of Galway, Ireland
Emer. Prof. Maria Lazaridou, School of Biology, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece
Morwenna Le Guillou, Centre de cancérologie Gustave Roussy, faculté de médecine Paris Saclay, France
Nolwenn Le Guyader, Ph.D. student, CEFÉ, Université de Montpellier, France

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Dr. Chantal Le Mouël, France
Klara Leander Oh, M.Sc., Wageningen University and Research, The Netherlands
Dr. Antoine Leblois, Environmental Economist, INRAE, France
Raphael Leblois, INRAE - CBGP (Montpellier, France)
Dr. Gernot Lechner, Department of Operations and Information Systems, University of Graz, Austria
Julia Lechtenberg, PhD student, University of Oldenburg, Germany
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Stephanie Leder-Büttner, Dept. of Urban and Rural Development, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), Uppsala, Sweden
Prof. Dr. Tosso Leeb, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland, Member Leopoldina (German National Academy of Sciences)
Dr. François Lefèvre, INRAE, France
Dr. Marine Legrand, Ecole Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées, France
Dr. Petteri Lehtikoinen, Finnish Museum of Natural History, University of Helsinki, Finland
Dr. Alekski Lehtikoinen, Finnish Museum of Natural History, University of Helsinki, Finland,
Dr. Thierry Lehner, astrophysique, Observatoire de Paris-Meudon, France
Dr. Irene Lehner, Lund university, Sweden
Sebastian Lehner, M.Sc., GeoSphere Austria, Austria
Dr. Christopher Leifsson, University of Turin, Italy
Prof. Dr. Reinhold Leinfelder (em.), Freie Universität Berlin & University College of Teacher Education Lower Austria
Dr. Bernd Leiss, Geoscience Center of the University of Göttingen, Germany
Dr. Eszter Lellei-Kovács, Ph.D., HUN-REN Centre for Agricultural Research, Institute for Soil Sciences
Pr. Servane Lemauviel-Lavenant, University of Caen Normandy, France
Prof. Dr. Peter Lemke (em), Universität Bremen & Alfred-Wegener-Institut Bremerhaven, Germany
Dr. Hartmut Lenhard, Zentrum für schulpraktische Lehrerbildung Paderborn, Germany
Prof. Luc Lens, Department of Biology, Ghent University
Prof. Dr. Andrea Lenschow, Osnabrück University, Germany
Dr. Guillaume Lentendu, Laboratory of Soil Biodiversity, University of Neuchâtel, Switzerland
Dr. Bernd Lenzner, Department for Botany and Biodiversity Research, University of Vienna, Austria
Benjamin Leon Bodirsky, Potsdam Institut für Klimafolgenforschung
Dr. Eric Léonard, Institut de Recherche pour le Développement, Montpellier, France
Prof. Dr. Sara D. Leonhardt, Technical University of Munich (TUM), Germany
Prof. Dr. Robert Lepenies, Karlshochschule International University
Prof. Jan Leps, University of South Bohemia in Ceske Budejovice, Czech Republic
Dr. Thibault Leroy, INRAE, France
Dr. Isabelle Letellier, Department of child and youth studies, Stockholm University
Prof. Dr. Christoph Leuschner, University of Göttingen, Germany
Dr. Cathy Liautard-Haag, University of Montpellier, France, Montpellier-Ecologie-Evolution-Biodiversity
Dr. Sabine Liebenehm, University of Saskatchewan, Canada
Prof. Susanne Liebner, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany
Prof. emer. Dr. Sigrid Liede-Schumann, University of Bayreuth, Germany
Dr. Juraj Lieskovský, Institute of Landscape Ecology, SAS, Slovakia
Dr. Jean-Marc Limousin, France
Dr. Olle Lindestad, Stockholm University, Sweden
Dr. JoAnne Linnerooth-Bayer, Equity and Justice Group, International Institute of Applied Systems Analysis, Laxenburg, Austria
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Sven Linow, Hochschule Darmstadt, Germany
Prof. Dr. Torsten Lipp, HS Neubrandenburg, Germany
Anna Lipsanen, M.Sc., Finnish Environment Institute, Finland
Dr. Pavol Littera, BROZ - conservation association, Slovakia
Dr. Audald Lloret-Villas, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Prof. Fiorella Lo Schiavo, University of Padua, President of Italian Society of Plant Biology, Italy
Prof. Dr. Andreas Lob-Hüdepohl, Katholische Hochschule Berlin, Germans
Dr. Ing. Karla E. Locher-Krause, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Leipzig, Germany
Anja Logo, Molecular Ecology, Agroscope, Switzerland
Dr. Madelon Lohbeck, Wageningen University, Netherlands
Dr. Miguel López Munguira, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain

Ing. Fernando López Santoveña, IATA-CSIC, Spain
Purificacion Lopez-Garcia, CNRS & Université Paris-Saclay
Guadalupe Lopez-Nava, Max Planck Institute for Biological Intelligence, Seewiesen, Germany
Dr. Armin Lorenz, University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany
Hannah Lou Kings, Ph.D., Maastricht Sustainability Institute, Universiteit Maastricht, Netherlands
Deral-Vella Louise, MC Student Master Biodiversity, Ecology, Evolution, University of Montpellier, France
Rui Lourenço, MED Mediterranean Institute for Agriculture, Environment and Development & CHANGE Global Change and Sustainability Institute, University of Évora, Portugal
Dr. Denis Loustau, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE) France
Dr. Maxime Louzon, Ecotoxicology Department, ENVISOL, France
Dr. David Löw-Beer, Research Institute for Sustainability (RIFS) at GFZ, Germany
Dr. Adeline Loyau, Toulouse Institut National Polytechnique, France
Yudi M. Lozano. Estacion experimental de zonas aridas (EEZA-CSIC), Spain
Dr. Friedrich-Karl Lücke, Fulda University of Applied Sciences, Germany
Dr. Amelie Luhede, Universität Oldenburg, Germany
María Luisa Arias Neira, Centro de Investigación en Sanidad Animal, CISA-INIA,-Agencia Estatal, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Madrid
Dr.ssa Erica Lumini, Italian National Research Council, Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection CNR-IPSP, Italy
Dr. Erica Lumini, Italian Research Council, Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection. CNR-IPSP, Italy
Dr. Geerts Luna, Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences and the Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research, Belgium
Prof. Helene Lundkvist, Swedish Univ. of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
Dr. Rachel Lupien, Aarhus University, Denmark
Inga Lutosch, Michael Succow-Stiftung
Dr. Lina Lüttgert, Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Germany
Prof. Holger Lutze, TUDarmstadt, Germany
Dr. Daniel Maag, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Germany
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Bea Maas, Department of Botany and Biodiversity Research, University of Vienna, Austria
Univ.-Prof. Dr. Axel Maas, Institute of Physics, University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Nicola Macchioni, Research Director, National Research Council of Italy, Institute of BioEconomy, Florence, Italy
Prof. Dr. Alceo Macchioni, University of Perugia, Italy
Lara Macheriotou, PostDoc, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Annie Machordom. Departamento de Biodiversidad y Biología Evolutiva. Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (MNCN-CSIC), Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Spain
Dr. Manuel J. Macía, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain
Prof. Dr. Ir. Steven Maere, VIB-UGent Center for Plant Systems Biology, VIB-Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium
Prof. Wouter H. Maes, Department of Plants and Crops, Ghent University, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Dirk Maes, Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO), Belgium
Prof. Elena Maestri, Università degli Studi di Parma, Italy
Timo Maier, M.Sc., Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR), Germany
Prof. Michela Maione, Università di Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy
Dr. Eléonore Maitre-Ekern, Norwegian Institute for Water Research, Norway
Dr. Aleksandra Majič Skrbinišek, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
Dr. Abdullah Makkeh, University of Göttingen, Germany
Dr. Kasja Malkoc, Max Planck Institute for Biological Intelligence, Germany
Dr. Gertraud Malsiner-Walli, Vienna University of Economics and Business, Austria
Prof. Dr. Joaquim Mamede Alonso, Life and Earth Sciences, proMetheus Unit Research, IPVC, Portugal
PhD Candidate Murugash Manavalan, MSc, Charles University, Czech Republic
Prof. Dr. Stefan Mangelsdorf, Hochschule der Deutschen Gesetzlichen Unfallversicherung (HGU)
Esteban Manrique Reol, Real Jardín Botánico - CSIC. Madrid. Spain
Dr. Muammar Mansor, University of Tübingen, Germany
Dr. Michael Manthey, Greifswald University, Germany
Dr. Elina Mäntylä, University of Turku, Finland
Agostino Manzato, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR - ISAC), Italy
Sarah Manzer, WueLAB Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Deutschland

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Prof. Stefano Manzoni, Department of Physical Geography and Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Stockholm University, Sweden

Dr. Maria Mar Delgado, Biodiversity Research Institute (CSIC/PA/UO), Asturias, Spain

Dr. Alfred Mar, Int. Association for Cereal Science and Technology, Austria

Prof. Sara Marañón-Jiménez, Center of Ecological Research and Forestry Applications (CREAF), Bellaterra, Barcelona, Spain

Dr. Arnald Marcer, Researcher, CREAM, Autonomous University of Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Catalonia, Spain

Dr. Lorène J. Marchand, Plants and Ecosystems Laboratory, Department of Biology, University of Antwerp, Universiteitplein 1, 2610 Wilrijk, Belgium

Javier Marchena Hurtado, Ph.D. researcher at Charité Universitätsmedizin, Germany

Dr. Aitor Marcos, University of the Basque Country EHU, Bilbao, Spain

Dr. Antoni Margalida, Pyrenean Institute of Ecology (CSIC), Jaca, Spain

Prof. Giovanni Marin, Università di Urbino Carlo Bo; SEEDS; FEEM, Italy

Federica Marini, M.Sc., University of Copenhagen, Denmark

Dr. Emma-Liina Marjakangas, Aarhus University, Denmark

Dr. Tim Mark Ziesche, Julius-Kuehn Institute, Germany

Prof. Dr. Thomas Marke, Department of Geography, University of Innsbruck, Austria

PD Dr. Michael Marks, University Tübingen, Germany

Hanna Rae Martens, University of Greifswald, Partner in the Greifswald Mire Center, Greifswald, Germany

Dr. Francisco Martín Azcárate, Departamento de Ecología & Centro de Investigación en Biodiversidad y Cambio Global (CIBC-UAM). Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. Spain

Dr. Jeanmougin Martin, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, France

Dr. Romina Martin, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden

Dr. Carlos A. Martín, Department of Biodiversity, Ecology and Evolution. Faculty of Biological Sciences. Complutense University of Madrid, Spain.

Prof. Dr. Dominik Martin-Creuzburg, Department of Aquatic Ecology, BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg, Germany

Dr. Luis Martín-Domingo, Ireland

Prof. Dr. Federico Martinelli, University of Florence, Italy

Andres Martinez de Velasco, M.Sc., Ghent University, Belgium

Dr. Javier Martínez-López, Ecology Department, University of Granada (Spain)

Dr. Carlos Martínez-Núñez, Department of Ecology and Evolution. EBD-CSIC, Spain

Dr. Felipe Martínez-Pastor, University of León, León, Spain

Prof. Jordi Martínez-Vilalta, Univ. Autònoma Barcelona & CREAM, Spain

Filipe Martinho, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Dr. Christina Martini, Leipzig University & German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig, Germany

Dr. Nuno Martins, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

Dr. Cristina Marzachi, CNR-Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Italy

Dr. André Mascarenhas, Institute of Landscape Planning and Ecology (ILPÖ), University of Stuttgart, Germany

Prof. Stefania Masci, PhD

Prof. Dr. P. Mascini, Erasmus School of Social & Behavioural Sciences & Erasmus School of Law, Erasmus University Rotterdam

Dr. Tereza Mašková Ph.D., Institute of Ecology and Evolution, Friedrich-Schiller University Jena, Jena, Germany

Dr. Joan Maso, CREAM, Fac. Ciències, Campus UAB, Barcelona, Spain

Dr. Jordi Massagué, IDAEA-CSIC, Spain

Dr. Valérie Masson-Delmotte, Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace, Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, Membre du Haut Conseil pour le Climat, Membre de l'Académie des Technologies, Membre de l'Académie des Sciences

Dr. Vanessa Masterson, Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS), Sweden

Dr. Amanda Mateo-Beneito, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Czechia

Pr. Jérôme Mathieu, Institute of Ecology and Environmental Sciences, Sorbonne University France

Dr. Miguel G. Matias, Departamento de Biogeografía y Cambio Global, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, MNCN-CSIC, Spain

Dr. Michael Matiu, Department of Civil, Environmental and Mechanical Engineering (DICAM), University of Trento, Italy

Dr. Kevin Matson, Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands
Prof. Dr. Jannika Mattes, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Germany
Antoine Mauclet, doctoral researcher, psychological department, UCLouvain, Belgium
Dr. Volker Mauerhofer, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Pascal Maugis, Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, Saclay, France
Dr. Philipp Maurischat, Carl-von-Ossietzky University Oldenburg, Germany
Dr. Matthias May, University of Tübingen, Germany
Ángeles G. Mayor, Ph.D., Faculty of Biological Sciences, Complutense University of Madrid, Spain
Prof. Dr. Olga Mayoral García-Berlanga, University of Valencia
Prof. Dr. René Mayrhofer, Johannes Kepler University Linz, Austria
Dr. Rachel Mazac, Stockholm University, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Sweden
Naomi Mazzilli, Avignon Université, Avignon, France
Dr. Camila Mazzoni, Evolutionary Genetics Department, Leibniz Institute for Zoo and Wildlife Research, Germany
Dr. Joshua McCluskey, Tübingen University, Germany
Dr. Eliot McIntire, University of British Columbia, Canada
Dr. Henning Meesenburg, Northwest German Forest Research Institute, Göttingen, Germany
Liam Megill, PhD student, Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR) / Delft University of Technology, Germany
Dr. Sandra Meier, Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity at the University of Oldenburg (HIFMB), Oldenburg, Germany
Dr. Fred Meier, Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
Dr. Joana Meier, Wellcome Sanger Institute, United Kingdom
Prof. h.c. Günter Meinert, Technical University Berlin, Germany
Frank Meinhardt, Umweltbundesamt, Germany
Prof. Dr. Anke Meisert, Institut für Biologie & Chemie, Universität Hildesheim
Prof. i.R. Dr. h.c. Dieter Meissner, Phys. Chem., LIOS, Johannes Kepler University, Linz, Austria
Dr. Ana Mendes, Invited Principal Researcher, MED –Mediterranean Institute for Agriculture Environment and Development, University of Évora, Portugal
Glenda Mendieta-Leiva, Biology Department, Phillips University of Marburg, Germany
Dr. Irene Mendoza, University of Sevilla, Department of Plant Biology and Ecology, Spain
Moritz Menken, M.Sc., Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR), Germany
Maja Menzel, Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, Germany
Thomas Merckx, WILD, Biology Department, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Brussels, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Joachim Mergeay, Research Institute for Nature and Forest / KU Leuven, Belgium
Dipl. -Ing. Kevin Merl, Institute of Hydrobiology and Aquatic Ecosystem Management, BOKU University, Austria
Dr. Elodie Merlot, INRAE, F-35000 Rennes, France
Dr. Andrew Merrie, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
Prof. Dr. Jan Mertens, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Stien Mertens, Research Institute for Nature And Forest, Brussels, Belgium
Dr. Geoffrey Mesbahi, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Switzerland
Dr. Angelika Meschede, PAN München, Germany
Dr. Mathis Messenger, Centre National de la recherche scientifique (CNRS), France
Daniel Messling, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany
Dr. Monika M. Messmer, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Switzerland
Prof. Géza Meszéna, Physics, Eötvös University & Institute of Evolution, Budapest, Hungary
Prof. Dr. Johannes Metz, University of Hildesheim, Germany
Dr. Paul Meulenbroek, BOKU University, Austria
Dr. Félicien Meunier, Q-ForestLab, Department of Environment, Ghent University, Belgium
Yvonne Meyer, B.Sc., University of Tuebingen, Germany
PD Dr. habil. Carola Meyer, Universität Osnabrück, Institut für Physik, Germany
Dr. Katrin Meyer, University of Göttingen, Germany
Dr. Prof. Patrick Meyfroidt, Earth and Life Institute, UCLouvain & F.R.S.-FNRS, Belgium
Dr. Delphine Mézière, Directorate of Open Science, INRAE, France
Prof. Dr. Bruno Mezzetti, Marche Polytechnic University, Italy
Dr. Isabelle Michallet, University of Rennes, France
Dr. Elisabeth Michel, Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, France

Prof. Dr. Nico Michiels, University of Tuebingen, Germany
Nathan Michielsen, M.Sc., University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Maja Mielke, University of Antwerp, Belgium
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Dr. Jean-Baptiste Mihoub, Sorbonne université, France
Dr. Lea Mikkola, Turku Bioscience Centre, University of Turku, Finland
Tibor Mikuska, B.Sc., Croatian Society for Birds and Nature Protection, Osijek, Croatia
Dr. Marija Miličić, Senior Research Associate at BioSense Institute – Research Institute for Information Technologies in Biosystems, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Rubén Milla, Instituto de Investigación en Cambio Global. Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain
Lucia Millan, M.Sc., CSIC - Institut de Ciències de Mar, Spain
Aisling Miller, M. Sc., Maastricht Sustainability Institute, Maastricht University, The Netherlands
Dr. Romain Minebois, Institute of Agrochemistry and Food Technology, IATA-CSIC, Spain
Saadia Mirza, Basiliense Fellow, University of Basel
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Dr. Julia Mitzscherling, Section for Geomicrobiology, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Bram Moeskops, FiBL Europe
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Dr. Gerald Moser, Plant Ecology, Justus Liebig University Giessen, Germany
Marta Mosna, Leibniz Institute for Zoo and Wildlife Research, Berlin, Germany
Dr. ir. Hans Motte, VIB-UGent Center for Plant Systems Biology, Ghent, Belgium
Dr. Thibault Moulin, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Dr. Patrik Mráz, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic
Dr. Stefan Mucha, Institute of Biology, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
Dr. Carolin Mügge, Research Group for Microbial Biotechnology, Ruhr Universität Bochum, Germany
Prof. Dr. Andreas Muhar, Boku University Vienna, Austria
Verena Mühlberger, Ph.D. student at GFZ Helmholtz-Zentrum für Geoforschung, Department Hydrology, Potsdam, Germany
Prof. Luciano Mule'Stagno, Inst. for Sustainable Energy, University of Malta
Matia H. Muller, Doctoral Researcher, Swiss Ornithological Institute
Dr. Emilie Muller, France
Prof. Dr. Stefan Müller, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
Prof. Dr. Daniel Müller, Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Countries (IAMO), Germany

Sina Müller, M.Sc., Alfred-Wegener-Institut, Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung; Universität Bremen, Germany
Dr. Claudia Müller, Monitoring Department, Swiss Ornithological Institute, Switzerland
Dr. Christoph Müller, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research, Germany
Dr. Max Müller, Technical University Darmstadt, Germany
Maximilian Müller, University of Greifswald, Germany
Kaja Müller, University of Greifswald, Germany
Markus Müllner, B.Sc., University of applied sciences vienna, Austria
Sifat Munim Tanin, Chair of Forest Entomology and Protection, University of Freiburg, Germany
Dr. Enrique Muñoz Ulecia, French National Institute for Agriculture, Food, and Environment (INRAE)
Estefanía Muñoz, Postdoctoral researcher, CREA, Barcelona
Dr. Jesús Muñoz, Royal Botanic Gardens, Madrid (CSIC), Spain
Dr. José Muñoz-Rojas, Universidade de Évora, Portugal
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Stephan Muth, M.Sc., Universität Regensburg, Germany
Dr. Sven Mutke, retired, Instituto de Ciencias Forestales, CSIC, Spain
Dr. Jens Mutke, Rheinische Friedrich Wilhelms-Universität Bonn, Germany
Apl. Prof. Dr. Michael Mutz, Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus – Senftenberg, Faculty Environment and Natural Science, Department of Freshwater Ecology, Germany
Prof. Dr. Bart Muys, Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, KU Leuven, Belgium
Neetash Mysuru, MPI BI-Seewiesen, Germany
Dr. Tobias Naaf, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Müncheberg, Germany
Dr. Lucy Victoria Naga, Heriot-Watt University, United Kingdom
Dr. Abhinav Naga, School of Engineering, University of Edinburgh, UK
Dr. Leopold Nagelkerke, Wageningen University & Research, The Netherlands
Dr. Tanvi Nagwekar, Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Germany
Dr. Dávid Nagy, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany
Dr. Francesca Napoleone, Department of Environmental Biology, University of Roma La Sapienza, Rome, Italy
Assoc. Prof. Naghmeh Nasiritousi, Linköping University, Sweden
Martina Natali, Italian National Research Council, CNR-IRPI, and KU Leuven
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Philippe Naveau, Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement
Prof. Valeria Negri, Università degli Studi di Perugia, Italy
Bhargavi Nerikar, M.Sc., University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Austria
Alexandra Nesterova, Biochemistry Division, University of Osnabrück, Osnabrück, Germany
Jun. Prof. Dr. Lena Neuenkamp, Bielefeld University, Bielefeld, Germany
Gerit Neuenschwander, B.Sc., Hochschule für Nachhaltige Entwicklung Eberswalde, Germany
Dr. Thomas Neumann, Borderstep Institute for Innovation and Sustainability, Flensburg, Germany
Dr. Jule Neumann, Department of Life Sciences, Aberystwyth University, Wales, UK
Astrid E. Neumann, M. Sc., Technische Universität München (TUM), Germany
Prof. Kimberly Nicholas, Lund University Centre for Sustainability Studies, Lund, Sweden
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Dr. Daniel Nickelsen, IT University Copenhagen, Denmark
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Prof. Dr. Matthew Nielsen, University of Bremen, Germany
Tanja Niemi, M.Sc., University of Jyväskylä, Finland
Dr. Laura Niessen-Wade, Maastricht Sustainability Institute, Maastricht University, Netherlands
Prof. Gonzalo Nieto Feliner, Royal Botanic Garden (RJB-CSIC), Spanish National Research Council, Spain
Dr. Reindert Nijland, Marine Animal Ecology group, Wageningen University, Wageningen, The Netherlands
Monika Niklaus-Ruiz, Dipl.-Biol., University of Würzburg, Germany
Dr. Natacha Nikolic, PhD, INRAE & University of Toulouse 3, CNRS, CRBE, France

Prof. Dr. Andreea Nita, Center for Environmental Research and Impact Studies (CCMESI), University of Bucharest
Dr. Michela Nocetti, Institute of Bioeconomy, National Research Council, Italy
Dr. Dominik Noll, University of Évora, Portugal
Prof. Dr. Benjamin Nölting, Hochschule für nachhaltige Entwicklung Eberswalde
Prof. Kevin J. Noone, Stockholm University, Sweden
Anke Nordt, Universität Greifswald, Germany
Nausicaa NORET, Lecturer, Université libre de Bruxelles, Belgium
Nikolaos Ntelkis, Ghent University
Dr. Biruk Nurihun, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
Dr. Matthias Nuss, Senckenberg Naturhistorische Sammlungen Dresden
Nicolas Nusser, M.Sc., Uniklinik RWTH Aachen, Germany
Dr. Darren O'Connell, University College Dublin, Ireland
Dr. Thomas Oberhänsli, Research Institute for Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, Switzerland
Prof. Dr. Klaus Obermayer, Fakultät IV, Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
Dr. Wolfgang Obermeier, Physical Geography, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Germany
ao. Prof. Dr. Gerhard Obermeyer, Membrane Biophysics, Dept. Biosciences & Med Biology, Univ. Salzburg,
AUSTRIA
Dr. Gabriele Obst, Evangelisches Gymnasium Nordhorn, Germany
Dr. Carolina Ocampo Ariza, Technische Universität Darmstadt, Darmstadt, Germany
Dr. Erik Öckinger, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
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Dr. Dörte Ohlhorst, Technical University Munich (TUM), Germany
Dr. Bettina Ohse, University of Potsdam, Germany
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Assoc. Prof. Milan Ončák, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Prof. Dr. Lars Opgenoorth, Philipps-Universität Marburg, Germany
Dr. Steffen Oppel, Swiss Ornithological Institute, Seerose 1, 6204 Sempach, Switzerland
Dr. Ildikó Orbán, Universität Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Niall Origo, Ghent University, Belgium
Aivars Ornicāns, Research assistant, Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava", Latvia
Prof. Simone Orsenigo, Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of Pavia, Italy
Dr. Francesco Orsi, Wageningen University, Netherlands
Dr. Joaquín Ortego, Doñana Biological Station (EBD-CSIC), Spanish National Research Council, Seville, Spain
Prof. Rene Orth, University of Freiburg, Germany
PhD Sarah Orth, University of Toulouse, France
PD Dr. Volker Ossenkopf-Okada, I. Physikalisches Institut, Universität zu Köln, Germany
Prof. Dr. Claus-Dieter Osthövener, Marburg University, Germany
Prof. Jan-Christoph Otto, Universität Salzburg, Austria
Prof. Dr. Ilona M. Otto, University of Graz, Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change, Austria
Dr. Wim A. Ozinga, Team Vegetation and Landscape Ecology, Wageningen Environmental Research, Wageningen,
The Netherlands
Adj.Asst. Prof. Dr. Petar Ozretić, Ruđer Bošković Institute, Croatia
Mirjam Paasch, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Maciej Pabijan, Institute of Zoology and Biomedical Research, Faculty of Biology, Jagiellonian University,
Kraków, Poland
Dr. Thais Pacheco Menezes, Earth and Life Institute, UCLouvain Belgium
Dr. Laurent Pagani, Observatoire de Paris & CNRS, Paris, France
Dr. Dr. Brigitte Pakendorf, CNRS, France
Dr. Sara Palacio, Tenured scientist at Instituto Pirenaico de Ecología (IPE-CSIC), Jaca, Spain
Dr. Thomas Palberg, Institute of Physics, Faculty of Physics, Mathematics and Informatics, Johannes Gutenberg
University, Mainz, Germany
PD DDr. Isabella Pali, University of Veterinary Medicine, Austria

Laurent Palka, CESCO, MNHN, Paris, France
Dr. Marlene Palka, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Germany
Dr. Javier Palma Guerrero, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, Switzerland
Dr. Rossel Pamela, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Germany
Jaroslava Panáková, Institute of Ethnology and Social Anthropology, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Slovakia
Marc Pananceau, Université Paris-Saclay, France
Dr. Giulia Panegrossi, Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate, National Research Council, Rome, Italy
Prof. Roberto Papa, Agricultural Genetics, Università Politecnica delle Marche, r.papa@univpm.it
Dr. Nikos Papandroulakis, Hellenic Center for Marine Research, Greece
Dr. Tobias Pape Thomsen, Department of People & Technology, Roskilde University, Roskilde, Denmark
Prof. Maria-Teresa Paramio, Animal Science, Univ. Autònoma Barcelona
Dr. Vishal Parekh, Department of Sustainable Development, Environmental Science and Engineering (SEED), KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden
Dr. Josephine Paris, Colorado State University, USA, University of Milan, Italy
Dr. Guillaume Paris, CRPG, Université de Lorraine-CNRS, Nancy, France
Dr. Barbora Parizkova, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Umeå, Sweden
Prof. Louisa Parks, Università di Trento, Italy
Giorgio Parlato, Ph.D. Student, Stockholm Resilience Center, Stockholm University
Prof. Richard Parncutt, University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Gema Parra, University of Jaén, Spain
Dr. Unai Pascual, Basque Centre for Climate Change, Leioa, Bizkaia, Spain
Dr. Ioannis Patramanis, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Dr. Sinikka J. Paulus, Max Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry, Jena, Germany
Dr. Raphaël Paut, INRAE, UMR Agronomie, Palaiseau, France
Ine Pauwels, Research Institute For Nature and Forest, Brussels, Belgium
Dr. Diego Pavón-Jordán, Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA), Norway
Bernard Payraastre, University of Toulouse, France
Dr. Robert Pazur, Institute of Geography, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Slovakia
Dr. Guy Pe'er, UFZ – Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research and German Centre for "Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig, Germany
Dr. Marc Peaucelle, Institut National de recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement, Bordeaux, France
Dr. François Peaudecerf, Institute of Physics of Rennes, University of Rennes, France
Jonathan Peel, ETH Zürich, Switzerland
Charlotte Peitz, M.Sc., Thünen Institute of Rural Studies, Germany
Eng. Venina Peixeiro, University of Évora, Portugal
Prof. Irene Pellegrino, Università del Piemonte Orientale, Italy
Prof. Dr. Sabine Penschel-Maier, University of Education Freiburg, Germany
Dr. Jose Matías Peñas Castejón, Universidad de Murcia, Spain
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Mariya Peneva, University of National and World Economy (UNWE), Department of Natural Resources Economics, Agribusiness, Food and Environmental Economics Research Center
Dr. Frank Pennekamp, University of Zurich, Switzerland
Dr. Benjamin Percival, Dept. Natural Sciences, Manchester Metropolitan University, United Kingdom
Dr. Andrés Peredo Arce, Senckenberg Research Institute, River Ecology and Conservation Department, Germany
Kiran Pereira, M.Sc., Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
Prof. Laura Pereira, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
Dr. Grégoire Perez, Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD)
Dr. Cristian Pérez-Granados, Forest Science and Technology Center of Catalonia (CTFC), Solsona, Spain
Dr. David Peris Navarro, Institute of Agrochemistry and Food Technology, Spain
Dr. Bálint Pernecker, University of Pécs, Hungary
Michiel Perneel, Ph.D. Researcher, Universiteit Gent, Belgium
Isak Perotti, PhD student, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
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Dr. Tomas Persson, Centre for Mathematical Sciences, Lund University, Sweden
Lorenz Peschel, University of Greifswald, Germany

Prof. Em. Dr Theodora Petanidou, University of the Aegean, Greece
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Jana Petermann, Department of Environment and Biodiversity, University of Salzburg, Austria
Dr. Frank B. Peters, Leibniz-Universität Hannover, Germany
Kristin Peters, M.Sc., Kiel University, Germany
Jan Peters, Michael Succow Stiftung, Partner in the Greifswald Mire Centre
Prof. Dr. Silke Petersen, Universität Hamburg, Germany
Prof. Garry Peterson, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
Dr. Catrin Peterson, Université Rennes 2, France
Dr. Eric Petit, INRAE, France
Hugo Peyriere, M.Sc./PhD Candidate, Montpellier University, France
Dr. Vera Pfannerstill, Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Germany
Dr. Simone Pfeiffer, University of Goettingen, Germany
Christine Pfeifle, Max-Planck-Institute for Evolutionary Biology, Germany
Dr. Laurette Piani, CRPG, CNRS-Lorraine University, France
Rafael Pichler, M.Sc., Delft University of Technology, Netherlands
Moritz Pichler, M.Sc., Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change, University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Peter-Paul Pichler, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research, Germany
Gaëlle Picon, Ph.D. student, CEFÉ, Université de Montpellier, France
Luc Justus Pienkoß, University of Rostock, Geodesy and Environmental Informatics
Prof. Dr. Meike Piepenbring, Goethe-University Frankfurt am Main, Germany
Julia Imola Piko, M.Sc., Forest Nature Conservation Group, University of Göttingen, Germany
Dr. David Pinaud, Centre d'Etudes Biologiques de Chizé, CNRS - La Rochelle Université, France
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Dr. Mikołaj Piniewski, Warsaw University of Life Sciences (SGGW), Warsaw, Poland
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David Pires, University of Évora, Portugal
Prof. Marina Piria, University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Fisheries, Apiculture, Wildlife management and spec. zoology, Croatia
Dr. Christophe Piscart, CNRS, UMR Ecobio, France
Ricardo Pita, MED –Mediterranean Institute for Agriculture Environment and Development, University of Évora, Portugal
Prof. Andrea Pitacco, University of Padua, Italy
Dr. Guillaume Piton, University Grenoble Alpes, France
Ambre Placide, Department of Ecology, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Samuel Planet-Duelli, PhD student, University of Graz, Austria
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Dipl.-Inform. Frank Pläßmeier, Germany
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Jeanne Poughon, Centre d'Ecologie Fonctionnelle et Evolutive, Montpellier, France
Prof. Marc Poujol, University of Rennes, France
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Prof. Karel Prach, University of South Bohemia, Budweis, Czech Republic

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Prof. Dr. Viola Priesemann, Max Planck Institute for Dynamics and Self-Organization, Göttingen, Germany
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Dr. Lucas Prost-Boxoen, Ghent University, Belgium
Saskia Proumen De Keyser, M.Sc., Belgium
Prof. Dr. Diogo Provete, Universidade Federal de Mato Grosso do Sul, Brazil/Italy
Dr. Rémi Prudhomme, Centre de coopération internationale pour l'agriculture et le développement, CIRAD-UMR CIREN, Montpellier, France
Dr. Felix Przesdzink, Department of Biology/Chemistry, Osnabrück University, Germany
Dr. Maria Stefania Przybylska, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany
Dr. Marios Psarianos, Leibniz Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy, Germany
Dr. Ewald Puchwein, Leibniz-Institut für Astrophysik Potsdam, Germany
Prof. Francisco I. Pugnaire, Estación Experimental de Zonas Áridas, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Almería, Spain
Prof. David Pulido-Velazquez, Spanish Geological Survey-Spanish Research Council (IGME-CSIC). Department of Water and Global Change
Prof. Petr Pyšek, Czech Academy of Sciences, Institute of Botany, Průhonice, Czech Republic
David Pytlík, M.Sc., Universität Greifswald, Germany
Prof. Dr. Volker Quaschnig, Berlin University of Applied Sciences HTW Berlin
Prof. Dr. Xavier Querol, IDAEA-CSIC, Spain
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Dr. Philippe Quirion, CIREN, CNRS
Dr. Gabriela Quiroga, Spain
Dr. Clemens Raab, Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austria
Dr. Viktoriia Radchuk, Leibniz Institute for Zoo and Wildlife Research, Berlin, Germany
Dr. Marco Radke-Fretz, KISTERS, Germany
Hugo Raguet, Institut National des Sciences Appliquées and University of Tours, Blois, France
Prof. Stefan Rahmstorf, University of Potsdam, Germany
Dharanish Rajendra, University of Würzburg, Würzburg, Germany
Dr. Álvaro Ramírez García, Departamento de Biodiversidad, Ecología y Evolución. Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Wanja Rast, M.Sc., Leibniz Institute for Zoo and Wildlife Research, Germany
Luca Räther, M.Sc., Greifswald University, Greifswald Mire Center, Germany
Dr. Gabriele Rathgeb, University College of Teacher Education Tirol, Austria
Dr. Leonie Ratzke, Johann Heinrich von Thünen Institute Federal Research Institute for Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries
Prof. Dr. Alexandra Rau, EH Darmstadt, Germany
Michel Raymond, CNRS, Institut des Sciences de l'Évolution Montpellier, France
Dr. Ernesto Recuero, Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain
Dr. Sarah Redlich, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Germany
Guislaine Refrégier, Lab. of Ecology, Society and Evolution. Université Paris-Saclay, France
Prof. Dr. Kira Rehfeld, swarken@iup.uni-heidelberg.de, Germany
Prof. Dr. Peter Reichl, University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Neil Reid, Reader in Conservation Biology, School of Biological Sciences, Queen's University Belfast, Northern Ireland (UK)
Susanne Reisner, M.Sc., University of Vienna, Austria
Thomas Rellensmann, Department of Environmental Economics, Osnabrück University, Germany
Prof. Ewa Rembiałkowska, Warsaw University of Life Sciences, Institute of Human Nutrition, Warsaw, Poland
Jaume Reñé, Spain
Dr. Natalia Revilla-Martín, Forest Science and Technology Centre of Catalonia, Spain
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Andrea Reyes, Université de Montpellier & Reserva: The Youth Land Trust
Dr. Klaus Rheinberger, FHV - Vorarlberg University of Applied Sciences, Austria
Hervé Richard, DRem CNRS, Chrono-environnement, Besançon, France

Wibke Richter, Doctoral Researcher at University of Greifswald, Greifswald, Germany
Prof. Dr. Hedwig Richter, Universität der Bundeswehr München, Germany
Prof. Felix Riede, Aarhus University, Denmark
Dr. Marc Riera Domínguez, Centre for Ecological Research and Forestry Applications (CREAF), Catalonia, Spain
Dr. Friederike Riesch, Grassland Science, University of Göttingen
Dr. Michael Rietsche, Goethe Universität Frankfurt am Main, Germany
Nadine Rijdsdijk, Ph.D. Student, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Tony Rinaud, Independent researcher, France
Dr. Thomas Rink, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Karlsruhe, Germany
Dr. Adrian Rinscheid, University of St. Gallen, Switzerland
Camille Risi, Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique
Prof. Dr. Geta Risnoveanu, University of Bucharest, România
Dr. Riccardo Riva, Delft University of Technology, Delft, The Netherlands
Dr. Francisco Robledano-Aymerich, Departamento de Ecología e Hidrología, Universidad de Murcia, E-30100 Espinardo (Spain)
Dr. Bjorn Robroek, Department of Ecology, Radboud Institute for Biological and Environmental Sciences, Radboud University, Nijmegen, Netherlands
Prof. Dr. Flavio Rocas, Biocenter, University of Würzburg
Dr. Miguel Rocha de Sousa, Department of Economics, University of Évora, CICIP & CEFAGE, SEDES and Ordem dos Economistas, Portugal, Chair RC35 Tech & Development IPSA & SASE
Juan Rocha, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
DI Dr. Philipp Rode, Austria
Dr. Juliane Röder, Philipps-Universität Marburg, Germany
Dr. Alexandra Rodriguez, Misión Biologica de Galicia-CSIC, Spain
Prof. Dr. Wolf Rogowski, Universität Bremen, Germany
Dr. Pascal Niko Rohrbeck, Max Planck Institute for Polymer Research, Mainz, Germany
Veronika Rohr-Bender, Max Planck Institute for Biological Intelligence, Seewiesen, Germany
Dr. Paula Romanovska, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research, Germany
Marvin Röndigs, B. Sc. University of Greifswald, Germany
Dr. Katja Rönkä, Ecology and Evolution of Interactions, Faculty of Biological and Environmental Sciences, University of Helsinki
Dr. Anna Roschanski, Universität Greifswald, Germany
Dr. Christoph Rosche, Institute of Geobotany, Martin-Luther-University Halle, Germany
Françoise Rose, CNRS, France
Prof. Daniele Rosellini, University of Perugia, Italy
Prof. Dr. Michael Rosenberger, Katholische Privatuniversität Linz, Austria
Dr. Marika Rossi, CNR Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection, Italy
Pr. Benoit Rossignol, Avignon Université, France
Stephanie Rost, Doktorand, Gothenburg University, Sweden
Prof. Dr. Antje Rothe, Katholische Hochschule für Sozialwesen Berlin (KHSB), Berlin
Jakob Johannes Rottmann, B.Sc., University of Innsbruck, Austria
Dr. Josselin Rouillard, Ecologic Institute, Germany
Daniel Rozua, PhD, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Spain
priv. Doz. Dr. Martin Rubey, Austria
Dr. Luisa Rubino, CNR Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection, Italy
Vicente Rubio Juan, German Aerospace Center, Germany
Prof. Diego Rubolini, Dipartimento di Scienze e Politiche Ambientali, Università degli Studi di Milano, Milano, Italy
Dr. Johannes Rüdiger, University of Innsbruck
Dr. Fabian A. Ruedenauer, Technical University of Munich (TUM), Germany
Dr. Janine Rüegg, Brandenburgische Technische Universität Cottbus-Senftenberg, Germany
Dr. Adrian Ruicănescu, National Institute of Research and Development for Biological Sciences, Romania
Dr. Kalle Ruokolainen, Department of Biology, Aarhus University, Denmark
Prof. Dr. Henning Rust, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Dr. Rebecca Rutt, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Prof. Dr. Santi Sabaté, Researcher at CREA-UB, Professor UB. Ecology Section. Department of Evolutionary Biology, Ecology and Environmental Sciences (BEECA). Faculty of Biology, University of Barcelona

Prof. Dr. Silke Sachse, University of Würzburg, Germany
Ilja-Valentin Sagvosdkin, Ph.D. student, Berlin University of Applied Sciences HTW Berlin, Germany
Assoc. Prof. Dragica Šalamon, University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture, Croatia
Prof. Dr. Sergio Salazar-Galán, Agroecosystems History Laboratory, Department of Geography, History and Philosophy, Pablo de Olavide University, Sevilla, Spain
Dr. Pasquale Saldarelli, CNR Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection, Italy
Assoc. Prof. Martin Šálek, Institute of Vertebrate Biology, Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic
Prof. Dr. Rui Salgado, Universidade de Évora, Portugal
Dr. Tiina Salo, University of Helsinki, Finland
Dr. Maria Salomidi, Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Greece
Matthias Salomon, M.Sc., Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change, University of Graz, Austria
em. ord. Univ. Prof. DI. Dr. Gerd Sammerni, BOKU University Vienna, Austria
Paula Sanchez Alandete, University of Greifswald, Greifswald, Germany
Dr. Sergio Sánchez Carrillo, Antimicrobial Resistance and Microbial Ecology (ARME) Group University of Galway, Ireland
Dr. Rut Sánchez de Dios, Departamento de Biodiversidad, Ecología y Evolución. Universidad Complutense de Madrid. Spain
Anna Sánchez de Mingo, Fakultät für Agrar, Bau und Umwelt, Universität Rostock, Germany
Dr. Inés Sánchez Donoso, Doñana Biological Station (EBD-CSIC), Spanish National Research Council, Spain
Dr. Andrea Sánchez Meseguer, Real Jardín Botánico, CSIC, Madrid, Spain
Dr. Pieter Sanczuk, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Martha Maria Sander, Leibniz centre for agricultural landscape research (ZALF) e.V., Germany
Dr. Jörn Sanders, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, Switzerland
Prof. Dr. Mignon Sandor, USAMV Cluj-Napoca, Romania
Dr. Andrea Santangeli, Senior Scientist, IMEDEA-UIB-CSIC, Esporles, Spain
Prof. Dr. Jakob Santner, Justus Liebig University Giessen, Germany
Agustina Santullo Latorre, Ph.D. student, University of Antwerp
Dr. Estibaliz Sanz, Basque Centre for Climate Change, Basque Country, Spain
Dr. Hakan Saritas, Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ), Belgium
Prof. Dr. Juliano Sarmento Cabral, Ecological Modelling, Department of Plant Biodiversity, Bonner Institute for Organismal Biology, University of Bonn, Venusbergweg 22, 53115 Bonn, Germany
Prof. Dr. Jean-Pierre Sarthou, University of Toulouse - INP AgroToulouse, France
Dr. Thomas Sattler, Swiss Ornithological Institute, Switzerland
Dr. Birgit Sattler, University of Innsbruck, Department of Ecology, Innsbruck, Austria
Dr. Jorge Saturno, Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, Germany
Pascal Sauer, M.Sc., Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research, Germany
Dr. Matthew Saunders, Trinity College Dublin, School of Natural Sciences, Botany Discipline, Ireland
Dr. Anna Scaini, Department of physical geography, Stockholm University, Sweden
Prof. Massimo Scandura, University of Sassari, Sassari, Italy
Vincent Scao, Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, IPSL, Université Paris Saclay
Dr. Gerrit Schaafsma, Leiden University, Leiden, The Netherlands
Dr. Wolfgang Schaefer, Scientists for Future Osnabrück, Germany
Dr. Urs Schaefer-Rolffs, Leibniz Institute of Atmospheric Physics, Germany
Prof. Dr. Dr. Martina Schäfer, Center for Technology and Society, Technische Universität Berlin
Prof. Dr. Ralf B. Schäfer, Research Centre One Health Ruhr, Essen, Germany
Michael Schäfer, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Anke Schaffartzik, Central European University Vienna, Austria
Dr. Thomas Schalla, Ev. Dekanat Karlsruhe, Germany
Dr. Lena Schaller, Institute of Agricultural and Forestry Economics, BOKU University, Vienna
Paula Scharlach, Institute of Environmental Systems Research, University of Osnabrück, Germany
Finja Schaumann, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research-UFZ, Halle, Germany
Dr. Gregor Schaumann, Universität Würzburg, Germany
Prof. Dr. Johannes Fredericus Scheepens, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany
Dr. Lena Scheiffele, University of Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Stephanie Schelfhout, Forest & Nature Lab, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University
Lea Schenk, Department of Cognition, Emotion, and Methods in Psychology, University of Vienna

Dr. Frederik Schenk, Stockholm University, Sweden
Dr. Istvan Scheuring, Centre for Ecological Research, Budapest, Hungary
Lea Schewe, Ph.D. Researcher, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Belgium
Prof. Stefano Schiavo, Università di Trento, Italy
Katrin Schifferle, M.Sc., University of Potsdam, Germany
Prof. Dr. Menno Schilthuizen, Taxon Foundation, Naturalis Biodiversity Center, and Leiden University, Leiden, The Netherlands
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Rafaela Schinegger, Institute of Landscape Development, Recreation and Conservation Planning, BOKU University, Vienna, Austria
Dr. Thomas Schinko, Austria
Marielle C. Schleifer, Technical University of Munich (TUM), Germany
PD Dr. Christian Schleyer, Universität Kassel, Germany
Dr. Matthias Schlögl, GeoSphere Austria, Austria
Prof. Dr. Matthias Schmelzer, Norbert Elias Center for Transformation Design & Research, University of Flensburg, Germany
Prof. Dr. Friederike Schmid, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Germany
Prof. Dr. Friederike Schmid, Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz, Germany
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Wulf-Peter Schmidt, CBS University of Applied Sciences, Cologne, Germany
Marius Schmidt, Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany
Wolfgang Schmidt, Evangelische Landeskirche Baden, Germany
Helena Schmidt, Multi-Actor Systems Department, Delft University of Technology, The Netherlands
Prof. Dr. Maud Schmiedeknecht, ESB Business School, Universität Reutlingen, Germany
Max Schmit, M.Sc., University of Freiburg, Germany
Prof. Dr. Christine Schmitt, Universität Passau, Germany
Dr. Katharina Schneider, Deutsches Literaturarchiv Marbach, Germany
Andreas Schneider, M.Sc., University of Goettingen, Germany
Shawn Schneidereit, Department of Geography, Humboldt-Universität Berlin, Germany
Dr. Franziska Schnell, TUM München, Germany
Dr. Rainer Schödel, Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía (CSIC), Granada, Germany
Fabian Scholz, M.Ed., Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Faculty of Biology and Biotechnology, Germany
Univ.-Prof. Dr. Jürg Schönenberger, University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Benito Schöpke, University of Hildesheim, Germany
Prof.in Dr.in Barbara Schramkowski, Duale Hochschule Baden-Württemberg, Germany
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Birgit Schröder, Universität Rostock, Germany
Prof. Dr. Boris Schröder-Esselbach, Institute of Ecology, TU Berlin, Germany
Dr. Iljana Schubert, University of Basel & Zurich University of Applied Sciences, Switzerland
Prof. Dr. Lisa M. Schulte, Institute of Ecology, Evolution and Diversity, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany
PD Dr. Eva Schultner, University of Regensburg, Germany
Leonie Schulz, M.Sc., Technical University of Munich, Germany
Dr. Jennifer Schulz, University of Potsdam, Germany
Laura Schulze, Osnabrück University, Germany, Departement of Economics
Florian Schunck, Institute of Environmental Systems Research, University of Osnabrück, Germany
Imogen Schwandner, Humboldt-University Berlin
Erik Schwarz, M.Sc., Stockholm University, Sweden
Luana Schwarz, Max Planck Institute of Geoanthropology & Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research, Germany
Dr. Oliver Schweiger, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ Germany
Prof. Dr. Thomas Schwetz-Mangold, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany
Prof. Dr. Helmut Schwier, Universität Heidelberg, Germany
Dr. Murray Scown, Lund University Centre for Sustainability Studies (LUCSUS), Lund University, Sweden
Dr. Marcel Sebastian, Environmental Sociology and Transformation Research, TU Dortmund University, Dortmund, Germany
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Prof. Dr. Gernot Segelbacher, University Freiburg, Germany

Amalia Seguras Gonzalez, Universidad Miguel Hernandez, Elche
Prof. Beate Seibt, Department of Psychology, University of Oslo, Norway
Melissa Seidel, University of Greifswald, Germany
Dr. Thomas Seifert, Scientists for Future, Germany
Dr. Miriam Seifert, Universität Bremen and Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung, Germany
DDI Dr. Carina Seliger, BOKU University, Institute of Hydrobiology and Aquatic Ecosystem Management, Vienna, Austria
Pr. Marc-André Selosse, Muséum national d'Histoire Naturelle (Paris) and Institut Universitaire de France, Académie d'Agriculture de France, University of Gdansk
Hendrik Selzener, Universität Greifswald, Arbeitsgruppe Moorforschung, Germany
Dr. Lluís Serra, Font Roja Natura UA Scientific Station, University of Alicante, San Vicente del Raspeig, Spain
Dr. Marine Severin, Ghent University, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Jan Sevink, Institute for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Dynamics (IBED), University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam, Netherlands
Dr. Moritz Sexauer, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Germany
Hisham M. Shaikh, Ghent University, Belgium
Esha Sharma, M.Sc., Switzerland
Dr. Vasundhara Shaw, Jodrell Bank Centre for Astrophysics, University of Manchester, United Kingdom
Emma Shih Mendez, University of Vienna
Prof. Dr. Friedrich Sick, Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft (HTW) Berlin, Germany
Prof. Dr. Bernd Siebenhüner, Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg, Germany
Dr. Ina M. Sieber, Kassel Institute for Sustainability, Universität Kassel & Deutsches Institut für Wirtschaftsforschung DIW e.V. Berlin, Germany
Dr. Ina Sieber, Kassel Institute for Sustainability, Universität Kassel,, Germany
Prof. Dr. Heike Siebert, Kiel University, Germany
Dr. Johannes Signer, Wildlife Sciences, Faculty of Forest Science and Ecology, University of Göttingen, Germany
Lorenzo Silvestri, Dipl., University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Guillaume Simioni, INRAE Ecologie des Forêts Méditerranéennes, Avignon, France
Prof.i.R. Dr. Clemens Simmer, Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn, Bonn, Germany,
Dipl. Ing. Katrin Simon, Botanic Garden of the Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany
PhD Ondrej Simonik, Institute of Biotechnology, Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic
Prof. Nadja Simons, Chair of Conservation Biology and Forest Ecology, Biocenter, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Würzburg, Germany
Univ.-Prof. Dr. Gabriel Singer, Institute of Ecology, Innsbruck University, Austria
Anil Singh, PhD student, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
Dr. Daniela Sint, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Dr. Catarina Siopa, University of Freiburg, Germany
Prof. Dr. Harald H. Sitte, Medical University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Cheryl Sjöström, Lund University, Sweden
Prof. Alasdair Skelton, Stockholm University, Sweden
Iveta Škodová, Institute of Botany, Plant Science and Biodiversity Centre, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava, Slovakia
Dr. Eleonore Slabbert, Anhalt University of Applied Science & Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Science – UFZ, Germany
Dr. Ronald Sladky, Faculty of Psychology, University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Barbara Smetschka, BOKU University, Austria
Dr. Ena Smidt, BOKU University Vienna, Austria
Angus Smith, M.Sc., Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands
Dr. Lysanne Snijders, Behavioural Ecology Group, Department of Animal Sciences, Wageningen University, the Netherlands
Dr. Krzysztof Snopek, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Solveig N. Söding, Biologist University of Muenster (Alumni), Germany
Prof. Dr. Simon Sohre, Evangelische Hochschule Freiburg, Germany
Dr. Rahel Sollmann, Leibniz Institute for Zoo and Wildlife Research, Berlin, Germany
Dr. Martin Sommer, Deutscher Verband für Landschaftspflege, Ansbach, Germany

Dr. Frank Sommerlandt, Thünen-Institut für Biodiversität, Braunschweig, Deutschland
Jaewon Son, MA., Institute for Technology Assessment and Systems Analysis (ITAS), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Germany
Dr. Veronica Sondervan, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Lisa Sophie Walsleben, Technical University Berlin, Germany, Postdoc at the Center for Research on Environmental Decisions in Berlin
Dr. Floor Soudijn, Wageningen Marine Research, The Netherlands
Markéta Gabriela Soukupová, M.Sc., Institute of Botany Czech Academy of Science, Czech Republic
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Jürg Spaak, RPTU Kaiserslautern-Landau, Germany
Dr. Johannes Spaethe, Chair of Behavioural Physiology & Sociobiology, University of Würzburg, Germany
Vera Sparrman, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Prof. Dr. Robert Speijer, Belgium
Dr. Anet Spengler Neff, Switzerland
Dario Pascal Sperber, M.Sc., German Aerospace Center (DLR), Germany
Prof. Dr. Gabriele Spilker, University of Konstanz, Germany
Dr. Martin Spitaler, Max Planck Institute of Biochemistry, Germany
Dr. Paul Spitzner, Germany
Dr. Fabio Sporchia, Aalborg University, Denmark
Dr. Camillo Spöri, TUB, Germany
Eng. Jana Spulerova, PhD, Institute of Landscape Ecology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, Slovakia
Prof. Dr. Marc Stadler, HZI Braunschweig, Germany, Dept. MWIS and Technical University of Braunschweig, Institute for Microbiology
Univ. Prof. Dr. Sigrid Stagl, Institute for Ecological Economics, Vienna, University of Economics and Business
Prof. Dr. Alexandros Stamatakis, Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas, Greece
Dr. Orestis Stavrakidis-Zachou, Greece
Dr. Melanthis Stavroulaki, Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology and Aquaculture (IMBBC), Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR), Greece
Dr. Jacqueline Stefels, Groningen Institute for Evolutionary Life Sciences, University of Groningen, the Netherlands
PD Dr. Markus Steffens, Research institute of organic agriculture FiBL and Institute of Geography and Oeschger Center for Climate Change Research, Universität Bern, Switzerland
Prof. Dr. Johannes Steidle, University of Hohenheim, Germany
apl. Prof. Dr. Peter Stein, Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, Germany
Gregor Steinbeiß, M.A. B.Ed. B.Ed., Johannes Kepler Universität Linz, Austria
Dr. Bernhard Steinberger, GFZ Helmholtz-Zentrum für Geoforschung, Potsdam, Germany
Prof. Julia Steinberger, Institute of Geography and Sustainability, Faculty of Geosciences and Environment, University of Lausanne, Switzerland
Dr. Marc Steinmann, Chrono-Environnement, University Marie and Louis Pasteur, Besançon, France
J.M. Steinvoort, MSc., Delft University of Technology, Delft, The Netherlands
Michael Steinwandter, Ph.D., Soil Biologist/Zoologist, Bozen/Bolzano, Italy
Dr. Volker Stelzer, Karlsruhe Institut for Technology, Karlsruhe, Germany
David Stemmer, South Australian Museum, Australia
Prof. Dr. Friedemann Stengel, Theologische Fakultät, Martin-Luther Universität Halle-Wittenberg, Germany
Nils Chr. Stenseth, Professor of Ecology and Evolution, Centre for Ecological and Evolutionary Synthesis (CEES), the University of Oslo, Norway
Ing. Esteban Stephan, French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), France
Prof. Dr. Tobias Stern, University of Graz, Austria
Laura Stewart, PhD, Centre for Ecological Research and Forestry Applications, Spain
Katharina Stiehl, Department of Clinical and Health Psychology, University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria
Prof. Dr. Walter Stöcker, Johannes Gutenberg-University Mainz, Germany
Prof. Dr. Günther Stocker, University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Alexander Stockhammer, Department of Biochemistry, Universität Osnabrück, Germany
Prof. Dr. (em.) Jürg Stöcklin, Universität Basel, Schweiz
Prof. Pavel Stoev, National Museum of Natural History at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, Bulgaria
Dr. Bernhard Stoevesandt, Fraunhofer IWES, Germany
Dr. Arie Stoffelen, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Stefan Stoll, Trier University of Applied Sciences, Germany

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Prof. Jörg Stollmann, Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
Dr. Hanna Stolz, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture, Frick, Switzerland
Dr. Juliane Stolz, Technische Universität Dresden, Dresden, Germany
Prof. Dr. Mark Stoneking (retired), Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, Lyon, France
Prof. David Storch, Ph.D., Center for Theoretical Study & Department of Ecology of Faculty of Science, Charles University
Dr. Anne Elise Stratton, University of Hohenheim, Germany
Prof. Dr. Charlotte Streck, University of Potsdam
Prof. Nathaniel Street, Department of Plant Physiology, Umeå University, Umeå, Sweden
Nikos Streftaris, M.Sc., Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Greece
Prof. Wolfgang Streicher, Universität Innsbruck, Austria
Dr. Anna Streissler, Umweltdachverband, Austria
Chris Stretton, M.Neuro., Ph.D. candidate, Maastricht Sustainability Institute, Maastricht University, The Netherlands
Prof. Dr. Erhard Strohm, Universität Regensburg, Germany
Prof. Jeroen Struben, emlyon business school, France
Dr. Natalie Struwe, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Dr. Jessica Stubenrauch, Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research, Leipzig, Germany
Prof. Dr. Christian Sturmbauer, University of Graz, Austria
Thierry Suard, M.Sc., Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL, Switzerland
Dr. Zhanli Sun, Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies (IAMO), Germany
Assoc. Prof. DDr. Werner Suppanz, University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Laura Sutcliffe, Georg-August-University of Göttingen, Germany
ret. Prof. Dr. Uno Svedin, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University senior visiting, Sweden
Prof. Jens-Christian Svenning, Aarhus University, Denmark
Dr. Luke Sweeney, Dipartimento di Scienze, Università degli Studi Roma Tre, Italy
Zuzana Swiderska, Department of Zoology, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic
Prof. Krzysztof Świerkosz, University of Wrocław, Poland
Assoc. Prof. Elias Symeonakis, Manchester Metropolitan University, UK
Dr. hab. Katarzyna Szczepko-Morawiec, University of Lodz, Poland
Dr. József Szekeres HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Hungary
Dr. Sophie Szopa, Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, France.
Dr. Nikolaus Szucsich, ABOL, Natural History Museum Vienna
Dr. Olivier Talagrand, Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace, Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique, France
Rachele Tamburino, CNR-IBE, Italy
Dr. Garance Tanguy, Université de Montpellier, France
PD Dr. Franziska Tanneberger, University of Greifswald and Greifswald Mire Centre, Greifswald, Germany
Dr. Cécile Tannier, Théma CNRS-Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, Besançon, France
Dr. Delphine Tardif, Potsdam Institute for Climate Research Impact (PIK), Germany
Dr. Clara Tattoni, Università dell'Insubria, Italy
Dr. Florin Tatui, University of Bucharest, Romania
PD Dr. Gregor Taxacher, Fakultät für Humanwissenschaften und Theologie, TU Dortmund
Dr. Lisa Tedeschi, University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Arne Temmerman, VIB-UGent Center for Plant Systems Biology, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium
Dr. Ralph J.M. Temmink, Utrecht University, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, the Netherlands
Dr. Alicia Tenza Peral, Departamento de Ciencias Agrarias y del Medio Natural, Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain
Dr. Celine Teplitsky, France
PD Dr. Ulrich Terpitz, Dept. of Biotechnology and Biophysics, University of Würzburg, Germany
Noa Terracina, B.Sc., University of Halle, Germany
Dr. Julien Terraube, Office Français de la Biodiversité, France
Dr. Louise Terryn, Ghent University, Belgium
Vladyslav Teslia, Switzerland
Prof. Dr. Kristin Tessmar-Raible, University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Markus Thamm, Julius Maximilian University Würzburg, Würzburg, Germany
Dr. Gaël Thébaud, INRAE, France
Prof. Dr. Katharina Theis-Bröhl, University of Applied Sciences Bremerhaven, Germany

Dr. Gonçalo Themudo, researcher in genomics, CIIMAR, University of Porto, Matosinhos, Portugal
PD Dr. Gabriele Theuer, Pädagogische Hochschule Schwäbisch Gmünd, Germany
Prof. Dr. Jörn Theuerkauf, Museum and Institute of Zoology, Polish Academy of Sciences
Prof. Denis Thieffry, Ecole Normale Supérieure, 75005 Paris
Kaat Thienpont, Research Institute of Nature and Forest (INBO), Belgium
Theo Thivent-Vial, Marine environment engineer, Créocéan, France
PD Dr. Henri Thomassen, University of Tuebingen, Germany
Dr. Amibeth Thompson, University of Freiburg, Germany
Marijke Thoonen, Scientist & Ph.D.-student, Research Institute for Nature and Forest, Belgium
Prof. Sophie Thoyer, France
Prof. Rocco Tiberti, Laboratorio di Ecologia della Conservazione ed Ecotossicologia, Dip di Biologia Ecologia e Scienze della Terra – DiBEST, Università della Calabria P.te P. Bucci, Cubo 6/B, 87030 Rende CS, Italia
Prof. Dr. Katja Tielbörger, Plant Ecology Group, University of Tübingen, Germany
Dr. Bärbel Tiemeyer, Thünen Institute of Climate-Smart Agriculture, Germany
Prof. Britta Tietjen, Institute of Biology, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
Robert Timmers, Utrecht University, The Netherlands
Dr. Flora Tinya, HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Hungary
Dr. Léa Tison, INRAE UMR SAVE, Villenave d'Ornon, France
Dr. Florian Tolle, ThéMA CNRS-Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, Besançon, France
Tsvetelina Tomova, Lund University, Sweden
Dipl. Ing. Jano Topercer, Ph.D., Považské múzeum, Žilina, Slovakia
Dr. Diarmuid Torney, Dublin City University, Ireland
Matilde Torrassa, Ph.D. student, DIBRIS, University of Genova, Italy
Alexandra Tost, Doctoral Researcher, Research Institute for Sustainability at GFZ, Germany
Prof. Dr. Chadi Touma, Dept. of Behavioural Biology, Osnabrück University, Germany
Dr. Rémi Tournebize, France
Dr. Samuel Tozer, CNRS, Institute of Biology of Ecole Normale Supérieure, Paris, France
Jonas Trepel, M.Sc., Aarhus University, Denmark
Dr. Gabriele Trespidi, Department of Biology and Biotechnology, University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy
Prof. Dr. Andreas Tribsch, Department of Ecology and Biodiversity, University of Salzburg, Austria
Dr. Andreas Tribsch, University of Salzburg, Austria
Prof. Dr. Rita Triebkorn, University of Tübingen, Germany
Dr. Silvia Trini Castelli, National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Italy
Margot Trinquier, CNRS, France
Prof. Dr. Michael Tritthart, BOKU University Vienna, Austria
Dr. Claus O.W. Trost, Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austria
Dr. Heimo Truhetz, Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change, University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Minh-Xuan Truong, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
Dr. Matthias Tschumi, Ecological Research Unit, Swiss Ornithological Institute, Sempach, Switzerland
Dr. Rigas Tsiakiris, forest ecologist, Member of the Board of Agroforestry Network of Greece & Scientific associate Green Institute Greece
Prof. Dr. Eeva-Stiina Tuittila, University of Eastern Finland, Finland
Dr. Laura Tuominen, University of Jyväskylä / JYU.Wisdom, Finland
Dr. Anne Turbe, Ecoscope, Haifa, Israel.
Jens Martin Turowski, Senior Scientist, Section 4.6 Geomorphology, GFZ German Research Center for Geosciences, Telegrafenberg, 14473 Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Alina Twerski, Vegetation and Landscape Ecology, Department of Agriculture, Ecotrophology and Landscape Development, Anhalt University of Applied Sciences, Bernburg, Germany
Prof. Dr. Rossen Tzonev, Sofia University "Kliment Ohridski", Department of Ecology and Environmental Protection, Sofia, Bulgaria.
Dr. Martina Überall, Pädagogische Hochschule Tirol / University College of Teacher Education Tyrol, Austria
Hannah Uhrmann, M.Sc., University of Bayreuth, Germany
Dr. Wiebke Ullmann, University of Potsdam, Plant Ecology and Nature Conservation, Germany
Dr. Susann Ullrich, Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft Berlin, Germany
Dr. Fabrizio Ungaro, National Research Council of Italy, Institute of BioEconomy, CNR IBE
Assoc. Prof. Thomas Unger, University College Dublin, Ireland

Dr. Elisabeth Unterfrauner, Centre for Social Innovation (ZSI), Vienna, Austria
Dr. Matthias Urban, Laboratoire "Dynamique du langage", Centre de la Recherche Scientifique, France
PD Dr. Astrid Utler, University of Bayreuth, Germany
Dr. Radovan Václav, Institute of Zoology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava, Slovakia
Dr. Csaba Vad, HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Budapest, Hungary
Valeria Valanne, MSc, Ph.D. student, Finnish Museum of Natural History, Helsinki, Finland
Vasilis Valavanis, Hellenic Center for Marine Research, Athens, Greece
Dr. Lorena Valdivia Steel, Independent Researcher, Germany
Dr. Francisco Valera, Estación Experimental de Zonas Áridas, CSIC
Dr. Orsolya Valkó, Institute of Ecology and Botany, HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Vácrátót, Hungary
Dr. David Valls-Gabaud, CNRS, Observatoire de Paris, France
Yannick Van Belle, Research Institute for Nature and Forests, Brussels, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Steven Van Belleghem, Department of Biology, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium
Caroline van Bers, University of Twente, Netherlands
Ir. Toon Van Daele, Research Institute for Nature and Forest, Belgium
Prof. Yves Van de Peer, VIB-Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Viktor Van de Velde, Department of Green Chemistry and Technology, Ghent University, 9000 Gent, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Ellen Van De Vijver, Ghent University, Belgium
Antoine Van de Vloet, M.Sc., Ghent University, Belgium
Prof. Dr. ir. Jan Van den Bulcke, Department of Environment, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, UGent, Belgium
Arwen van der Gugten, M.Sc., Wageningen University & Research, The Netherlands
Dr. Sancia van der Meij, University of Groningen
Dr. Michiel van der Molen, Wageningen University, The Netherlands
Ir. Mark van der Poel, Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands
Prof. Maja van der Velden, Dept. of Informatics, University of Oslo
Prof. Dr. Peter van Dongen, Johannes Gutenberg-University Mainz, Germany
Dr. Anne van Doorn Wageningen Environmental Research, the Netherlands
Leen Van Gijssel, M.Sc., Ghent University, Belgium
Nick Van Hee, Department of Bioscience Engineering, University of Antwerp, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Mark van Kleunen, Department of Biology, University of Konstanz, Konstanz, Germany
Dr. Roel van Klink, Martin-Luther-University Halle-Wittenberg, Halle (Saale), Germany
Bob van Leeuwen, Wageningen University & Research, the Netherlands
Prof. Geert van Loo, VIB-UGent Center for Inflammation Research, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Koenraad Van Meerbeek, Belgium
Hugo Van Nieuwenhove, Doctoral researcher, Department of Earth and Environmental Science, KULeuven, Belgium
Dr. Mark van Nieuwstadt, Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, the Netherlands
Dr. R.M.R. van Oosten, Faculty of Archaeology, Leiden University
Johanna Van Passel, Ghent University, Belgium
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Martijn van Praagh, Lund University - Centre for Environmental and Climate Science, Sweden
Dr. Fabienne Van Rossum, Meise Botanic Garden, Belgium
Dr. Kevin Van Sundert, Maastricht University, The Netherlands
Jasper Van Vlasselaer, Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, Belgium
Dr. Arnold van Vliet, Wageningen University & Research, The Netherlands
Dr. Jeroen Van Wichelen, Research Manager at Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO), Brussels, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Frieke Vancoillie, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Kris Vandekerckhove, Senior researcher forest ecology – Research Institute for Nature and Forests, Brussels, Belgium
Dr. Pieter Vangansbeke, Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO), Belgium
Dr. Margot Vanhellemont, Research Institute for Nature and Forest, Belgium
Dr. Ruben Vanholme, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Thomas Vanneste, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium
Dr. Marco Varricchione, University of Molise, Italy
Alessandro Vasta, United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization, Rome, Italy
Sergio Velasco Ayuso, University of Buenos Aires, Argentina
Dr. David Vendrami, Bielfeld University, Germany

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Prof. Mario Veneziani, University of Parma, Italy
Alfredo Venturo, Czech University of Life Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic
Prof. Hans Verbeeck, Q-ForestLab, Department of Environment, Ghent University, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Frederick Verbruggen, Department of Biology & Department of Experimental Psychology, Ghent University, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Ir. Peter Verburg, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, the Netherlands
Dr. Pieterjan Verhelst, Research Institute for Nature and Forest, Belgium
Prof. Dr. ir. Kris Verheyen, Department of Environment, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, UGent, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Elie Verleyen, Ghent University, Faculty of Sciences, Belgium
Alex Vermeulen, M.Sc., ICOS ERIC - Carbon Portal / Lund University, Sweden
Dr. Pasqua Veronico, CNR Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection, Italy
Prof. Dr. Dirk Verschuren, Ghent University, Belgium
Dr. Bas Verschuuren, Forest and Nature Conservation Policy group, Wageningen University, The Netherlands
Prof. Dr. Jonathan Verschuuren, international and European environmental law, Tilburg University, Netherlands
Dr. Cyprien Verseux, University of Bremen, Germany
Dr. Iva Veseli, Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity, Germany
François-Xavier Viallon, Universität Osnabrück, Deutschland
Prof. Dr. Sara Vicca, Department of Bioscience Engineering, University of Antwerp, Belgium
Dr. Joana Vicente, CIBIO-InBIO BIOPOLIS, Portugal
Prof. Dr. Elena Viganò, University of Urbino Carlo Bo, Italy
Dr. Matthieu Vignal, Avignon Université, laboratoire ESPACE, France
Dr. Astrid Vik Stronen, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia
Dr. Alberto Vilagrosa, Univ. Alicante, Spain
Dr. Pablo Villalva, Aarhus University, Denmark
Dr. Catherine Villard, CNRS & Université Paris Cité, Paris, France
Prof. Sebastian Villasante, Director EqualSeaLab-CRETUS, University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain
Dr. Dani Villero Pi, Centre de Recerca Ecològica i Aplicacions Forestals (CREAF), Campus UAB, Edifici C. 08193 Bellaterra (Barcelona), Spain
Dr. Gregoire Vincent, Institut de Recherche pour le développement, France
Doc. Michal Vinkler, Univerzita Karlova, Praha, Czech Republic
Jannis Viola, Alfred-Wegener-Institut, Earth System Diagnostics Group, Potsdam, Germany
Prof. Ginés Viscor, Universitat de Barcelona, Spain
Dr. Simon Vitecek, BOKU University – Institute of Hydrobiology and Aquatic Ecosystem Management, Vienna, Austria
Prof. Dr. Oliver Vitouch, Universität Klagenfurt, Österreich
Dr. Amarante Vitra, Research Institute for Organic Farming (FiBL), Switzerland
Dr. Maria Vives-Ingla, Centre for Research on Ecology and Forestry Applications (CREAF), Cerdanyola del Vallés, Barcelona, Spain
Prof. Dr. Lothar Vogel, Facoltà Valdese di Teologia, Rome, Italy
Dr. Sebastian Vogel, Leibniz Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy (ATB), Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Matthias Vögeli, Applied Ecological Research Unit, Swiss Ornithological Institute, Sempach, Switzerland
Bianca Voicu, Msc, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden
Dr. Hartmut Voigt, FESH, Freie Evangelische Schule Hannover, Germany
Prof. Alexey Voinov, University of Twente, Netherlands
Dr. Florence Volaire, INRAE, Center for Ecology, Montpellier, France
Prof. Dr. Filip Volckaert, Department of Biology, KU Leuven, Belgium
Dr. Rebecca Volkmann, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences Potsdam
Prof. Dr. Doris Vollmer, Max Planck Institute for Polymer Research, Mainz, Germany
Dr. Maria von Balthazar, University of Vienna, Austria
Dr. Claudia von der Mark, VIB-UGhent, Belgium
Prof. Dr. Sophie von Merten, University of Salzburg, Austria
Dr. Jonathan von Oppen, University of Basel, Switzerland
Dr. Frederik von Reumont, Institute for Geography Education, University of Cologne
Dr. Dirk von Schneidmesser, Research Institute for Sustainability at GFZ, Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Tobias Vorlaufer, Leibniz Center for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Germany
Prof. Dr. Matthijs Vos, Ruhr University Bochum, Germany

Charles Vuillermin, Ph.D. student, laboratoire Chrono-environnement, Université Marie et Louis Pasteur, Besançon, France
Prof. Dr. Stéphane Vuilleumier, Université de Strasbourg, France
Dr. Ján Výboštok, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Institute of Geography, Comenius University and Faculty of Natural Sciences, Department of Regional Geography and Regional Development, Bratislava, Slovakia
Prof. i.R. Dr. Ulrike Wagner-Rau, Ev.Theol. Fakultät, Philipps-Universität Marburg
Marie Wahl, BSc, BOKU University, Institute of Hydrobiology and Aquatic Ecosystem Management, Vienna, Austria
Dr. Ida Wallin, Southern Swedish Forest Research Centre, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
Dr. Sebastian Walter, Freie Universität Berlin
Franziska Walther, M.Sc., ETH Zürich, Switzerland
Ronald Walusimbi, M.Sc., Osnabrueck University, Germany
Dr. Magnus Wang, WSC Scientific GmbH, Heidelberg, Germany
Dr. Sophie Warken, Heidelberg University, Germany
François Warlop, Groupe de Recherche en Agriculture Biologique, Avignon, France
Prof. Dr. Dirk Wassermann, IU Internationale Hochschule Bremen
Dr. Ulrich Weber, Lüner Initiative gegen globale Armut, Germany
Prof. Dr. Bettina Weber, University of Graz, Holteigasse 6, 8010 Graz, Austria
Dr. Nicholas Wei Cheng Tan, Southeast Asian Rainforest Research Partnership (SEARRP)
Prof. Dr. Antoinette Weibel, University of St. Gallen, Switzerland
Prof. Dr. Alexandra Weigelt, Leipzig University (Germany)
Dr. Fabian Weikl, Technical University of Munich, Germany
Prof. Florian Weiler, Department of Public Policy, Central European University
Prof. Dr. Luzian Weisel, Vice President, German Society for Information and Knowledge, Frankfurt
PD Dr. Linda C. Weiss, Ruhr University Bochum, Department of Animal Ecology, Evolution and Biodiversity, Universitätsstr. 150, 44801 Bochum
Prof. Dr. Michael Weiß, Steinbeis-Innovationszentrum Organismische Mykologie und Mikrobiologie, Germany
Dr. James Weldon, Researcher, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Boris Weliachew, Ph.D., Architect/Civil Engineer specialized in Major Risks Mitigation, lecturer-researcher at the National Graduate School of Architecture Paris Val de Seine (ENSAPVS) and the EVCAU research laboratory, international expert EC/UN/ISDR in Eco-Resilience, and OMSC/GUARAMBÁ scientific expert
Dr. Frido Welker, Globe Institute, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Prof. Dr. Kristin Wellner, Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
Dr. Franziska Wenskus, Universität Duisburg-Essen, Germany
Prof. Renate A. Wesselingh, Earth & Life Institute, UCLouvain, Belgium
Coen Westerduin, Ecology and Genetics Research Unit, University of Oulu, Finland.
Prof. Serge Wich, School of Biological and Environmental Sciences, Liverpool John Moores University, UK
Prof. Dr. Anja Widdig, University of Leipzig, MPI EVA and iDiv
Dr. Dominik Wiedenhofer, BOKU University, Austria
Levin Wiedenroth, PhD, University of Potsdam, Germany
Dr. Markus Wiederstein, University of Salzburg, Austria
Prof. Dr. Claudia Wiegand, UMR 6553 ECOBIO, University Rennes, France
Prof. Dr. Kerstin Wiegand, University of Göttingen, Germany
Silvia Wiegel, Ph.D. student and research assistant, University of Bayreuth, Food Sociology, Germany
Dr. ir. Jan J. Wieringa, Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, The Netherlands
Katharina Wieser, M.Sc., University of Graz, Austria
Dr. Rotraud Wieser, Medical University of Vienna, Austria
Jule Wilberg, (BA), Environmental Sociology and Transformation Research, TU Dortmund University, Dortmund, Germany
Katharina Wilbrand, Chair of Hydrology, University of Freiburg, Germany
Prof. Lena Wilfert, University of Regensburg, Germany
Dr. Håkan Wilhelm Hugosson, Faculty of Engineering and Sustainable Development, Department of Electrical Engineering, Mathematics, and Science, University of Gävle, Gävle, Sweden
Kerstin Wilhelm, Ulm University, Evolutionary Ecology and Conservation Genomics, Germany
Dennis Wilke, PhD student, Osnabrück University, Germany
Dr. Franziska Willems, University Marburg, Germany

Dr. Tim G. Williams, Senior Scientist, Institute for Agricultural Policy and Markets, University of Hohenheim, Germany

Dr. Andreas Wilting, Leibniz Institute for Zoo and Wildlife Research, Berlin, Germany

Dr. Josefin Winberg, Lund University, Sweden

Univ.-Prof. (i.R.) Ing. Dr. phil. Dr. h.c. Verena Winiwarter, formerly BOKU, Vienna, Austrian Academy of Sciences

Univ.-Prof. Dr. Lukas Winiwarter, Universität Innsbruck, Austria

Dr. Carolin Winter, Chair of Environmental Hydrological System, University of Freiburg, Germany

Dr. Marten Winter, German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig, Germany

Prof. Rasmus Winther, Globe Institute, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

Prof. Dr. Han Wiskerke, Department of Social Sciences, Wageningen University, The Netherlands

Prof. Dr. Ulrike Witten, LMU Munich, Germany

Edith Wittenbrink, Lic. theol., Faculty of Theology and Religious Studies, KU Leuven, Belgium

Dr. Burghard Wittig, Institut für Ökologie und Evolutionsbiologie, Vegeta Universität Bremen

Lisa-Christin Wlodkowski, Doctoral Researcher, GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany

Kathrin Wollenweber, B.Sc., University of Tübingen, Germany

Dr. Sabine Wollrab, Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries, Germany

Dr. Grace Wong, Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden

Dr. Anna Woodhead, Stockholm University, Sweden

Prof. Dr. Nicole Wrage-Mönnig, Grassland and Forage Sciences, University of Rostock, Germany

Dr. Maarten Wubben, Rotterdam School of Management, The Netherlands

Prof. Dr. Agnes Wuckelt, Catholic University of Applied Sciences NRW, Germany

Prof. Angela Wulff, University of Gothenburg, Biological and Environmental Sciences, Sweden

Jens Wunderlich, Michael Succow Foundation, Greifswald, Germany

Prof. Dr. Rolf Wüstenhagen, University of St. Gallen, Switzerland

Dr. Ana Maria Yañez-Serrano, IDAEA-CSIC, Spain

Dr. István Zachar, HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Institute of Evolution

Prof. Dr. Sabine Zachgo, Osnabrueck University, Germany

Dr. Maja Zagamajster, Assist.prof., University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Slovenia

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Johann G. Zaller, Institute of Zoology, Department of Ecosystem Management, Climate and Biodiversity, BOKU University, Vienna, Austria

Valeria Zambianchi, Postdoctoral researcher, Earth and Life Institute, UC Louvain, Belgium

Dr. Shokufeh Zamini, Austrian Institute of Technology, Austria

Caroline Zanchi, Freie Universität Berlin

Prof. Dr. Karim Zantout, Karlsruhe University of Applied Sciences, Karlsruhe, Germany

Dr. Kathi Zarnack, Theodor-Boveri-Institute, Julius Maximilian University Würzburg, Würzburg, Germany

Giorgio Zavattoni, M. Sc., Doctoral researcher, Department of Biology, University of Turku, Finland

Dr. Eliska Zaveska, Institute of Botany, Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic

Doz. Dr. Harald G. Zechmeister, Dept for Botany and Biodiversity Research, University of Vienna, Austria

Prof. Dr. Thomas Zeilinger, Philosophische Fakultät und Fachbereich Theologie, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany

Prof. Dr. Regina Zeitner, Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft, Germany

Dr. Yuval Zelnik, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden

Dr. Lei Zhang, University of Birmingham, UK

Dr. Elisa Ziegler, University of Tübingen, Germany

D.Sc. Urszula Zielenkiewicz, Institute of Biochemistry and Biophysics PAS, Warsaw, Poland

Dr. Caroline Zimm, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Austria

Prof. Dr. Mirjam Zimmermann, Universität Siegen, Seminar für evangelische Theologie, Germany

Prof. Dr. Ruben Zimmermann, Centre for Ethics In Antiquity and Christianity, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität, Mainz, Germany

Dr. Elke Zippel, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

Dr. Maria Zozaya-Montes, CIDEHUS-University of Évora, Portugal

Dr. Marie-Katherin Zühlke, University of Greifswald, Germany

Prof. Dr. Pieter Zuidema, Wageningen University, Netherlands